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Change in mentality towards disabled people in Central Asia

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Abstract: In early societies, the disabled occupied the position of flawed, inferior, poor people: they were considered a burden, people unable to benefit. But before the Zoroastrian religion, the idea of physical defects was understood as a punishment for sins or as a sign of possession by evil spirits. This attitude towards the disabled often led to the fact that they were shunned, feared and considered outcasts of society. The daily lifestyle of people with physical and mental disabilities in those days turned into restriction and isolation, their exclusion from normal life, labor relations, creative spheres.

This article is about the tolerant attitude of people to the disabled. This is done in the Avestan meaning in relation to persons with disabilities. Since ancient times, people in the east have been treated with tolerance. The nature of the attitude towards disability and the life of each nation is based on the mentality and religious relations of this nation. In particular, in Central Asia in ancient times, human life was determined on the basis of religious beliefs. For example, there was a pre-Islamic religion Zoroastrianism. It has the words "good thoughts, good words, good work." This is proof of a tolerant attitude towards disabled people. The Holy Book of Zoroastrianism in Avesto also calls for tolerance attitude.

Key words: Avesto, vendidat, poor, blind, dumb, primitive community, relationship, land.

For those who have a long history of disability has been one of the main problems in this society since ancient times, and traces its history back to BC. Care for persons with disabilities, disability prevention and treatment issues in each period based on the characteristics of the mentality of the people has acquired a different character in different periods. During the primitive community to live in harsh living conditions of the people living in such conditions, only the survivors had to go. Still they are not installed any regard for people with disabilities. Compared to the limited possibility of early relationships formed in the land of mythology and religious views. This is natural, because the legendary outlook shared by a number of philosophical thought, and this was reflected by ancient thinker's looks. Relationship to the limited possibility of the first religious views, because it is formed only naturally. This legendary land of the mythological worldview shared by a number of philosophical thought in the middle of this ancient thinkers and looks.

The Zoroastrian religion is a period when there are significant changes in people's views on the nature of man himself, on the purpose and meaning of his life. Profound transformations in the spiritual life of ancient society are characterized by the emergence of new philosophical systems based on interest in real life, man, his purpose and place in society. People's minds were increasingly possessed by faith in the mind and strength of man. At this time, there are significant changes in attitudes towards people with disabilities. It took more than two thousand years to realize the necessity of caring for people with developmental disabilities and recognizing their right to exist. Humanists in the middle eages played a positive role in changing the attitude of society towards a person with physical and mental disabilities.

For example, the ancient Central Asian countries is one of the first written sources of information about the history of Avesta views. It has to highlight the issue of disability in the empty period, based on the spirit of determination, treatment and prevention of disabilities, a special Emphasis on the culture of health among the population. Zoroastrianism, the religion, coinciding with the emergency of seed systems-level society. Naturally to promote a new society Axuramazda[1]. Axrimon example of the power of the Evil one makes every effort to Indians in the work of the field in the research According to the H.Homidiy in Vendidad names are listed in the following diseases and is known about the sources of their origin: sudden death, there will be pain, and fever. Fever, pain in the brain agent[2]. Ajhu, was bitten by a snake, cars, hypertension, and eye view of the atmosphere, crust and Gandhi. Failure to Comply with the Majority of these ceremonies,

because of negligence, Barker and gandidosh (talismans, cancer) diseases Axrimon the seeds of the earth is called dry deliberate intention. The second part of the example in Vandida Avestos Vendidat Axura Mazda predictable construction of "disability, illness, mental Vulnerability Biography of Paradise" Wishful thinking about the country. Heresy and the mentally retarded Angra many viewed as that relay to the god of darkness. Avesta Disability generation to prevent than cure, special attention was given to the factors of the original. First, build the family of the young men and women to be healthy, flawless in every aspect. Secondly, pregnant women suffering. Irritability, and to consume more fruit, but found herself to eat the provision for fraud[3].

Therefore, the purpose of Acrimony's to prevent disease and disability through the prevention and reduction of disability in the afterland. The end of the 7th century BC thinker in the field of medicine, the treatment of the following methods: otashkas floor darmongoh (polyclinic), clinic (hospital) was established under the jurisdiction of the state of the industry, costs are covered at the expense of private property. Under the control of the state, of course, who improved treatments. Some physicians to treat patients with the good spirit in our power to encourage, with the power of some of his knowledge, treatment, and other physicians treating patients with iron master, and a variety of healers marazliklarni through various herbal healing to treat. While other types of prayer heals says[4]. Different treatment depending on the disease that can lead to disabilities. For example, the prayer will be a treat mentally retarded treatment of various tumor diseases by using a razor, herbal drink. Sometimes as a direct appeal to yazdan asking solve the problem, there are excerpts from the tone of the claims. Vendor's fiftieth fargard so, that all diseases were killed at the same time: term and no, they do not have all the illness formed. Avesta prayers through a variety of diseases, disabilities and prayer by priests shows treatment[5].

Therefore, we have some people with limited physical abilities to protest rising. Persons with disabilities to receive care and their situation has become an integral part of the national patrimony for centuries[6].

In conclusion, we can say that in the east, from the earliest days of human history, formed in connection with the care of people with disabilities. The first dishonoring the conditions of people with disabilities Central Asia in the ansient Ages disabilities on the basis of the principles of the Zoraastrizm religion, a sense of caring for the poor and lifestyle. Neighbors share mosques and madrasahs in shelters under poor and the needy and the neighbors who live near by meals. Therefore, we have some people with limited physical abilities to protest rising. Persons with disabilities to receive care and their situation has become an integral part of the national patrimony for centuries.

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Analysis of Postmodern Elements in the Novel *if on a winter's night a traveler* Written by Italo Calvino

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Abstract: Today, we live in the postmodern era, whose traces and signs can be seen everywhere, and ironically, this new fashion of contemporary intellectualism is the most comprehensive cultural attack on non-Arab societies that has been experienced so far. In post-modern stories, we are not facing a plot, and it is as if some kind of destruction and collapse has occurred in the plot, so that no order and coherence can be seen in its plot. Considering that postmodernism is one of the most important literary movements of the 20th century, and also because of the breadth and universality of this school, many researches have been conducted in this field, each of which has studied postmodernism from a specific perspective. Based on what was mentioned, the purpose of the study is to Analyze of Postmodern elements in the Novel *if on a winter's night a traveler* written by Italo Calvino. The study is placed in the position of descriptive-analytical studies. A comparative and scrutinizing examination of different dimensions and angles of the novel *if on a winter's night a traveler* shows that there are obvious and similar postmodern components in it such as multiple endings, contradictions in characters, deconstruction, metafictional layer, para-narrative, and short circuit. The results of this research can greatly contribute to literary studies.

Keywords: Postmodern Elements, Novel, *if on a winter's night a traveler*

1.1 Introduction

The term postmodernism is a literary movement that began in the mid-1960s with the attitude of traditional novels. This term is called the course of extensive developments in critical attitude, philosophy, architecture, art, literature and culture, which emerged from the womb of modernism and in reaction to it or as its successor (Economides, 2016). Today, we live in the postmodern era, whose traces and signs can be seen everywhere, and ironically, this new fashion of contemporary intellectualism is the most comprehensive cultural attack on non-Arab societies that has been experienced so far. In post-modern stories, we are not facing a plot, and it is as if some kind of destruction and collapse has occurred in the plot, so that no order and coherence can be seen in its plot (Elam, 2019). The reason for this is that the element of causality is missing here, the element that connects the execution of the plan in the story in a cause and effect manner. In this type of novel, there is basically no same ending and the reader can move the parts of the story without any change in its overall structure. Ontological content, the author's presence in the story, uncertainty, humor in the text, metafiction, lack of a fixed point of view, multiplicity of characters, etc. are characteristics of the postmodern story (Clare, 2019).

Considering that postmodernism is one of the most important literary movements of the 20th century, and also because of the breadth and universality of this school, many researches have been conducted in this field, each of which has studied postmodernism from a specific perspective. Some of these researches have been from the perspective of politics, education, philosophy, art and architecture, etc. But the investigation of this flow and approach in the field of literature is limited to brief researches that make the mind of every active researcher aware of how to investigate the most important literary flow of the 20th century in the field of literature (Evans, 2019). Also, unfortunately, in our country, whenever we talk about criticizing a work, they consider the interpretation of the meaning of the work or evaluate it as a good or bad work, and think that the work of the critic is to praise or despise the author and criticize its performance. However, one of the goals of this research is to remove the heavy shadow of this view from critics (Reinhoud, 2019). Nevertheless, postmodernism is one of the most important currents whose components have appeared in people's lives. And the novel is one of the literary forms that has a significant contribution in showing the human condition in the

world of modernity. So, the researcher will examine how the postmodern components are in the literary form of the novel, and for this purpose, he has chosen the novel *if on a winter's night a traveler* by Italo Calvino.

Italo Calvino, born in 1923, is a famous Italian storyteller who has his own literary style. Among Calvino's works, we can mention the trilogy of our ancestors (*The Baron in the Trees*, *The Nonexistent Knight*, and *The Cloven Viscount*), *Invisible Cities*, *Mr. Palomar*, etc. His work *if on a winter's night a traveler* is a novel full of enthusiasm to read, in which a post-modernist approach can be seen, among these components are incoherence, short circuit, pretense, uncertainty, escapist ideology, author's death, etc. pointed out (Calvino, 2013). The story is about a reader who starts reading Calvino's novel " *if on a winter's night a traveler* ", but at the end of the first chapter, he encounters another story, so he goes to the bookstore and protests, and the seller tells him He says that there was a mistake in the binding of this novel and it was mixed with the Polish version of the novel. So, he takes the Polish version of the book from the seller and continues reading the novel with a female reader whom he meets in the bookstore, and both readers come across half-complete versions of the narratives (ten stories) every time. They find out the stories behind these problems. At the end of the story, the male and female singers, who are now married, are busy reading the novel *if on a winter's night a traveler* by Calvino.

The novel *if on a winter's night a traveler* is actually a collection of stories that never end. One day, Mr. Reader buys a book and we start reading the story with him, but in an exciting place, the book ends and the angry reader goes to the bookstore, where he meets Miss Reader. They take the correct copy of the book and realize that it is a completely different story that cannot be continued due to bad printing, and in the same way we follow 10 half-finished stories in the main story of the book. The novel *if on a winter's night a traveler* first takes the reader to the back of the bookstore window and after a short pause, takes him inside to stop in front of a book shelf and with his sharp eyes and pre-prepared senses, in Look for Calvino's latest book among the shelves. "You see against the shelves books that have been read before they were printed." The book includes discussions on reading experiences and it seems that Calvino preferred reading to writing in this work (Kang, 2022).

On the other hands, what refers to the artificiality and premeditatedness of the text in postmodernist texts is the author's presence in the text and the reader's self-awareness and fakeness of the text. The author of this style talks about the writing process and its difficulties in order to challenge the structure and rules of writing with subtle humor (Makarushka, 1990). "You're about to read Italo Calvino's new story if you're traveling on a winter's night. Take it easy Concentrate" (p. 7). "Here, the story has a part of dialogue that has no function other than the introduction of daily life in a rural town" (p. 23). "The page you are reading should bring you back to the beginning... this unity includes a movement that tests a suitable text against another..." (p. 46).

Another component of postmodern texts is the selection of different methods and styles (combination of genres) as well as the use of multiple viewpoints to express the narrative. Calvino takes advantage of the combined point of view of the narrator and the second person to tell the story so that he can continue his games by telling the diary from the observer narrator, multiple first person narration and Silas Flannery's diary. Even in the continuation of his narrative, the author stops addressing the man and addresses the woman. "Miss reader, how are you? It's about time that this book is not opportunistic with the second person singular pronoun and only addressed to a male you or something similar to that or the brother of an opportunistic "I" and is only directly addressed to you..." (p. 172). By presenting the examples, in this thesis, an attempt is made to investigate the presence of postmodern elements in the novel with a descriptive and analytical method in order to determine the author's approach to postmodernism, which has been expressed in a different way. Based on what was mentioned, the main question of the study will be raised; what are the postmodern elements in the novel *if on a winter's night a traveler*?

1.2 Review of the Literature

In this part, the theoretical explanation of some of the constituent elements of postmodernism is discussed:

Deconstruction: The strong tendency to break pre-accepted structures, the dissolution of fixed norms and identities in individual, social and political life is one of the most obvious components of postmodernism, the most prominent representative of which is Jacques Derrida, whose readings of modern literature, along with his readings of Classical texts of philosophy have had the most powerful and at the same time the most fruitful consequences for contemporary thinking (Sookermany, 2017). The concept of structure and even the

word "structure" itself has an age equal to knowledge, that is, equal to western science and philosophy. The center of a structure, by directing and organizing the coherence of the system, provides an opportunity for its components to play within the overall framework (Caputo, 2007). A set of center-to-center replacements is considered as a connected chain. According to his opinion, breaking the foundation is a process to show how the clear messages of the author of a text and work are weakened and faded as a result of other aspects of the presentation of that work, and finally the main message of the author is under the influence of the secondary aspect and is forgotten (Moore, 2004).

The metafiction of self-awareness in the story: This term, which was first coined by the contemporary self-aware critic and novelist William S. Burroughs was used in one of his articles in 1970. Later, "Robert Schulz" popularized it, it refers to postmodernist stories that consciously and systematically draw the reader's attention to the fact that the world of the story is constructed and artificial and that this world does not refer to a world outside the world of the text (Johns-Putra, 2018). Attracts and challenges the relationship between fiction and reality in different ways. According to John Barthes, metafiction is a type of novel that imitates a novel instead of imitating the world (del Pont, 2019).

Suspense: breaking the story line and leaving it suspended, which deals with other discussions and even talks about the form of the story. In the term of story, it is called the state of uncertainty and expectation that the reader experiences towards the end of the story. As the plot of the story opens, the reader becomes curious about the end of the events and stays in a state of suspense (Bork, 2003). This sense of suspense and curiosity makes the author able to drag him with all his strength to the end of the story. This feature appears in the story in two ways, one is that the author brings up the secret in the story, an unusual situation that the reader is eager to describe and explain. Another thing is that it puts the characters of the story, both male and female, in a difficult situation, so that the character has to choose one between two actions and two ways, and sometimes these two actions and two ways are both undesirable, and choosing one of these two The way attracts the reader's attention more (Coles & Hall, 2001). The curiosity of the eager reader about following the events of the novel creates suspense, and if this suspense is combined with concern about the fate of a character, it reaches its maximum level. In industrial novels, suspense creates initial motivations for reading, but in popular times, which usually have a very adventurous plot, suspense is the author's main strategy to make the reader interested in reading the novel (Cordle, 2008).

Ambiguity of time and place: David Harvey considers the disintegration and multiple ruptures in the art of language and human psyche as the result of transformation in our attitude and perception of time and space. The history of capitalism produces what Harvey calls the density of space and time (Stephenson, 2008). The course of life has been towards acceleration and increase, and in parallel with the increase in density in space time, space has also contracted and condensed. Being influenced by incidents and events in regions thousands of miles away from the place of occurrence has become a normal and everyday thing for nations and people. He believes that fluidity, ephemerality, instability, mixing and decomposition and dispersion of postmodern artistic products. Like books, movies, architecture and art, they are only mirrors of this variable and flexible phenomenon (Scheurich, 2014). The compression and density of time and space, which is the consequence of the speed of communication and new industrial conditions, have blurred the national borders, and the globalization of capital has caused the mixing and fusion of nationalities. In his opinion, science-fiction stories called cyberpunk warn against a technological world that has turned man into a half-machine mixture, and have a postmodern nature (Hassan, 1985).

The author's lack of authority and the rebellion of the characters: Another feature of the realist story, that is, the author's unquestionable authority over the story and characters, is violated in metafiction. If the author in premodern literature created characters, events, and their destiny in a god-like and deterministic way, in beyond the story desperately runs after the characters of his creation and requests them to move the plot of the story forward, and in some cases he gives in to the characters' desire to figure out their own destiny (Trites, 1998). Characters who often do not have authority over their fate and for this reason, sometimes desperately want to escape from the story space. In this way, the postmodern novel is a mirror of the whole world and reflects its uncertainties and confusions and the inability of humans. Of course, the unquestionable and god-like authority of the author was first questioned in modernism, but this lack of authority in postmodernism is much more severe and different from modernism (Deer, 1994).

Ontological content: One of the important consequences of approaching the fictional world as another universe is a specific ontological boundary; The boundary that this approach draws around the fictional world at the cost of the inner ontological difference that may be revealed within this world in any way (Thouki, 2019). In fact, the only ontological difference that the other approach to the cosmos acknowledges is the contrast between the real and the fictional. Thomas Powell says that every ontology is a theoretical description of a universe. Martin Heidegger is one of the harbingers of postmodernism, who at the beginning used phenomenology in the direction of existentialism and searched for the meaning of "being", but after a while, he turned his attention from "being" to "being, which means the nature of existence (McHale, 2003). Brian McHale considers this very important component, which draws a content boundary between modernism and postmodernism, the main characteristic of postmodernism and the axis of other components. With the socio-economic changes of the advanced societies, naturally, cultural changes also occurred in all fields and primarily in the philosophical way of looking at the world. This change of attitude, which can be expressed in the transformation of epistemology into ontology, was also transferred to the field of art and literature, and according to McHale, it became the main characteristic of postmodern literature in the predominance of ontological content (Kroeze, 2011).

The characters of the metafiction of unity in the same multiplicity: The characters of the novel, despite having different names and taking part in different events, are united based on some clues and seem to have something in common with the author. The character in the postmodern story is always multiplying (Ashraf & Farooq, 2020). As a fictional character changes its name in different places of the story and takes on separate themes, but during the story, the multi-layered characters are one and the same. In some postmodern novels, the characters don't even have full names. Limiting these characters to the first letter of their first name and last name is a way to show the fact that the identity of humans no longer has any foundation, and instead of this foundation, there is now only a random and completely changeable set of individual characteristics (Pantaleo & Sipe, 2010).

Multiple appeals: Another way that the postmodern story questions the certainty and unity of the fictional world and basically the real world is multiple endings. And if the modernist author left the ending of his characters in an open and vague and foggy, half-finished space, the metafictional writer tries to guess all the possible endings and present them to the reader (Anderson, 2014). He asks the reader for his opinion about these appeals and leaves him free to choose; Endings whose simultaneous association is contradictory. In the postmodern story, the endings sometimes come in the form of multiple, fragmented and parallel alternatives that cannot happen at the same time; Sometimes it is presented in a false and artificial, indeterminate and probable, circular or based on retrogression left to the reader. So we see that postmodern literature is more realistic than any realism, in a very deep way, it reflects reality, but in a different way (Schrag, 1992).

Short-circuiting the interference of the real world with the fictional world: He considers an important characteristic of postmodern writings to be the blurring of the distance between the literary text (imagination and mental) and the real (objective) world. He surprises the reader by using a short circuit so that he empathizes with the character and does something so that he cannot easily place the metafiction in the common categories of literary texts (Huber & Huber, 2014). In order to create a connection, he used tricks such as combining different aspects of a story with aspects apparently based on reality in a single work, bringing up the author and authorship and bringing it into the text, revealing the customs and literary devices when using them, the author's conversation with The main character uses... but these tricks cannot be the inventions of postmodern writers. In this component, there is a connection between the story world and the real world (Medak-Seguín, 2016). In the short circuit, the writer enters the story and appears in the role of a writer in front of his characters. In postmodern stories, the author's presence in the story is often accompanied by the narrator's or fictional characters' inattention to him, and this is a trick to show the end of the author's authority. By using this trick, he wants to constantly remind the reader of what he is reading (Huber & Huber, 2014). It is just a story and not the reality itself to keep the reader alert until the end of the reading. Metafictional novels are attached to the concept of the author as the creator of the text; a text that exaggerates the presence of the author in relation to the story, the real author, repeatedly steps into the world of the story (Fales, 2005).

1.3 Methodology

This study is placed in the position of descriptive-analytical studies and examined the postmodern elements in the novel *if on a winter's night a traveler* by Italo Calvino.

1.4 results

Deconstruction: In Calvino's novel, the structure of Calvino's novel is not devoid of this characteristic and at the very beginning it shows itself very dizzying and unconventional for the reader, which is based on different limitations and discrete narratives but in an innovative way. It changes the content of each narrative, but preserves their internal structures: *You have always longed to get to know the real novelty that stays fresh once it is new, if you read a book as soon as it is published without imposing or chasing, you will have this newness at the very first moment. Will it happen this time? We never know... Wait, it's normal to be a little disappointed and confused at the beginning of reading... This book is independent from what you expected from the author... This book will stimulate your curiosity.*

Calvino wants the reader not to leave his novel for a moment. Tools are not important for him; He looks at his final thought and goal. The content of his narratives is not derived from strange and big events, but from the passing of the simplest and most detailed everyday events. By mentioning simple details in the form of narration, he has done an interesting deconstruction: *These are the pages of the book, which are like the windows of a train, they are old, cloudy, and the sentences are covered with a cloud of steam... As soon as the book is opened, the smell of fried oil escapes from the pages... The joys of using paper is tangible, audible, visible, and especially spiritual pleasure... The photocopy papers end there, but what is important for you from now on is to find the sequence of this writing... the first the feeling that this book should convey is my feeling when the phone rings, I say it should because I doubt that the written words can convey even a part of that feeling correctly All the ten books that started they evaporated in your hands and can be found in this library.*

The author even breaks the structure of single reading in his novel because by bringing male and female readers and accompanying them together until the end of the novel, he creates a new method that has attracted more external audience to continue reading the novel: *Mr. reader, this is the lady reader who has started her happy arrival on your horizons and attentions... two of us have a better chance to recreate a complete version. between the two readers, through the mediation of the book, a solidarity has been established What is more natural than this? We can exchange our readings. This injustice was brought to us by the publishing organization and it is he who must compensate for it. We have to go there to find out.*

Superstition: Contemporary metafiction draws the reader's attention to the fact that life, like a novel, is built within a framework, and ultimately it is impossible to understand where one structure ends and another framework begins. In metafiction novels, arrangements framing is clearly seen in a diverse range of stories; for example, a story within a story; Characters who are reading their fictional lives. This component in Calvino's novel with the metafictional presence of male and female author and reader and in the form of how to read and write the book from the beginning of the story with the author's remarks and addressing the reader in a way shows this feature in the text that continues until the end of the story, the author with Giving the role to the reader and putting his life to find the original version of his novel in the text of the stories of his time removes the constraints and the new model based on the transformation of reality in the metafictional story writing. The description of Calvino's first account of his book, which gave it a metafictional aspect, begins as follows: *"You read in the newspaper that if a night of Calvino's Nights was printed... you would go to a bookshop and buy it You have always longed to be acquainted with the real novel. Will it happen this time? We never know. ...the novel begins in a railway station. a cloud of smoke covers the first paragraph"*

In a part, the author asks his reader, who is very nervous about the incompleteness of the novel, to be grateful and tells him that he should control his anger. *We know that you have become more nervous, but you have learned to control yourself. What makes you angry is that you are grateful for the actions of people, carelessness, indiscretion, or others.*

The arrival of the narrator (writer) who regularly flaunts his presence in the course of the story in an excessive and clear way and by mentioning the disappearance and confusion of the pages of the novel and emphasizing this issue has shown the novel to be a fake work. Even the reader of the novel sometimes thinks that the author has put him to work: *"I have gotten into such a habit of not reading that I don't even read the writings that happen to me because every writing is not worth reading, even a book that was given to you as a gift or a text that you were forced to read. It is not easy to read until the end, we learn from childhood to just read"*.

Suspension: In his novel, Calvino keeps the reader in suspense by bringing diverse and half-finished narratives to discuss the issue of how to narrate events as an important issue. Each central movement of the story in the continuation of the novel is tied to the next narrative with a technical break in the area of the author's specific aesthetics: *The story of the strange man with a suitcase in his hand and wandering in the train station on a rainy night, right on the verge of killing an unknown man, remains unfinished, and this movement is the beginning of the suspension of the story, which continues in the same way in all narratives until the end of the tenth chapter. Of course, this interruption In addition to creation, suspense provides the possibility of thinking and active participation of the reader with the author to remove the suspense from the narratives by relating them to each other, but until the end of the story, the reader always sees the structure and content of the suspenseful text and ultimately himself. He decides to end this suspense in the novel by marrying the lady singer.*

Existential content: In Calvino's novel, the reader enters the thousand twos of the fictional world and the real world, from which it seems very difficult to escape. narratives in this novel is an example of disrupting the fixed logic of narration, every part of which is like stepping a character to the other side of ontology and entering another narrative level. In this novel, the ten narratives do not actually constitute a real time, because what they repeat. It is the partial aspects of the story and not its general and continuous aspects that only the nested criteria make their existence necessary. But there are two nested texts in the novel that are simply described from the real world: the first novel text It is from Hermes Marana, the translator, which is designed to permanently divert the attention of the Arab sultan so that he does not engage in the revolution as a joke and the sultan's wife, who loves to read, continues to read his stories in this way: *"Marana proposes to the Sultan a shakardi that is taken from the Eastern literary tradition of the book One Thousand and One Nights: it stops its translation at the moment of greatest suspense and begins to translate another story, inserting it into the first story. For example, a character in the first time opens a book and starts reading. The second novel is also interrupted until the third and fourth novels ad infinitum...."*

The character of the authors of the narratives: The identity of the authors of each narrative has been expressed with many names, all of which at the end of the story, are attributed to Calvino, the main author of the story "If a night ends". Of course, among the stories, there is also a mention of an Indian person nicknamed the father of narrations, which is a legend, and people believe that many of the stories written by famous authors have already been narrated by him, and Marana did this by recording his voice in the cave. and he has been called the universal source of the gem of narrations; Some consider him the living Homer or the author of One Thousand and One Nights, Alexandre Dumas and even Joyce, all of these names have made his identity seem fragmented and ambiguous in the novel. Of course, in the first chapter of the novel, where the main character calls himself "I", it causes the audience to doubt between his identity and the main author (Calvino), so that he is confused, this is me, the main character of the story, with the author of the novel: *My name is and this is the only thing you know about me, this is enough to create this desire in you to pledge a piece of yourself in this unknown me and know someone, just like the author himself, without asking Do I say anything or do I intend to name the character of his story, but to hide him from the eyes, I neither name him nor describe him, because all the names and descriptions describe him more than this simple pronoun. This simple work, which I wrote this word, included a little of myself and my feelings in it.*

In the middle of the story, Flannery, a writer who is suffering from a nervous breakdown, is introduced, and in front of him is Marana, a translator who falsifies his stories. Flannery expresses his opinion about his works, which was forged by Marana to name novels that never it is not written together, he says this so that he may know his identity as a true flâneur to his reader. *An unknown publisher gives the form of a book to those things that need to be defined, but no one has the time or the ability to write Maybe this is my real story and I have lost it, I could add to mine But if the only thing a book can have is an independent truth, then I can accept it and write my own truth. even though I am a writer whose writings can be falsified and people think it seems that I myself have the necessary qualities to grow up as a fraud in order to create perfect substitutes. If this uncertainty in the identity of the author forces the reader to surrender trust and to the silent voice of the storyteller, the foundation of literature is in the foundation. A permanent change was achieved.*

Multiple endings in Calvino's novel: A reader who thinks that every reading should have a final conclusion does not exist in Calvino's novel, but his half-finished and ambiguous narratives make the reader

unable to find a single conclusion for them. Although at the end of the story, the author expressed his opinion about the ending of the stories from the mouth of one of the readers, but he did not follow this characteristic, and the reader waits for the events and actions of the characters in the uncertain endings of each of his various narratives. He should start saying his guess: *In ancient times, the narratives had only two endings: the female hero and the male hero when they got out of all the trials, or they got married or they died. The ending that draws all the narratives there is a situation: either it continues in life or it is inevitable, death.*

In the beginning of metafictional novels, the author often talks openly about the arbitrary nature of the beginnings and the distinction between the beginning, the middle and the end, and the strongest endings in the postmodern story is the ending after which the audience's mind begins to think about the thought hidden in The story should be slow and in the direction of the content of the story, and in a way, at the end of the story, it will return to the beginning of the story. The uncertainty of the fate of characters such as: Mr. Kuderer, Alex Jasos, Nakho and even Marana the translator in each of the narratives until the end gives the audience the feeling that there was no reason to make all these efforts from the beginning, nothing has changed and all It has been fruitless. In a part of the story, the author expresses this feeling through the language of a character named master Tutzi, addressing the reader of the story as follows: *Don't ask me to find the sequel of the book, the continuation of all the books beyond... the books are the first step of the beginning.*

Contradiction: In his novel, Calvino also uses contradictory text views, one of the methods desired by the formalists to transform the plot into a story. If the confrontations slow down a bit, the reader will lose the text and the text of the audience. He has such a contradictory opinion about how to read a book that even though new books have an attractive appearance, no one will read them as soon as they become old, and also while reading, one should pay deep attention to parts of the book and It should be rejected in parts of this attention: *Books are familiar with this devilish beauty, the same beauty that has turned yellow until the back of the cover fades... When reading, you should be both inattentive and attentive... from the time you are captured by writing, I have lost the pleasure of reading.*

In another part, the author shows the contradiction in the analogy of his half-finished narratives with life being full of various events behind which there is nothingness and nothingness. And he believes that his novel in every chapter with this subtlety of found emotions suddenly breaks away from baseless confusion. Even the presence of contradictory elements in Calvino's time can be found in the way that at the beginning he invites the reader to read his book calmly, but then he deliberately puts the reader in trouble with his half-finished narratives, and the reader after a while who follows the study of the story, loses the desire to read and does not understand what the truth is and why these events happened.

Contradictions in characters: In the novel, the contradiction of the characters also shows itself in the forms of hesitation, the behavior of plural identity and the unknown ratio of the characters. Calvino shows the opposites in the form of two writers, one is wandering and the other is productive and perfect. He even searches for his ideals in introducing the perfect writer from the perspective of the audience: *The productive writer has a lot of regular writing, but the wandering writer tears every page he writes...if we accept that writing can be If the border of the author's limitations is crossed, then it becomes meaningful to be read by a certain person. The text is proven only in its ability to be read by a person... it must be read in order for the soul to live.*

Short Connection: Calvino has left a trace of himself in the form of each of the characters in the ten narratives of his novel as a first-person narrator and has brought it to its peak. And he establishes a connection with his reader and turns him from a passive audience to an active reader. It is because of the author's presence that the reader feels himself inside the story and every story that happens seems real to him. By creating the roles of female and male singers, he wanted to show his relationship with the world of the story in a natural way, so that he could somehow live in his own story by wandering through the singer's life. First special image: *You are starting to read Calvino's new story, calm down, concentrate... let the world around you hide behind the air... choose the most comfortable mode to read... it is not going to be in this The book is especially waiting for something special... Come on, Mr. Reader, this is the Lady Reader who has started her happy arrival on your horizons... So choose an interesting topic for conversation.*

By humorously explaining how to buy and write his novel, the author is in a way teasing the reader and making a joke with him. As the reader continues reading the novel, he thinks that Calvino is staring at him from outside the story. By tickling the reader's mind, he continues to narrate his unfinished stories and by

referring to the intellectual foundation of his novel, he emphasizes its independence: *With a sudden rush you reach the fortress of new books. After a quick look at the titles of the books on offer, your steps towards a pile of "If one of the winter nights a traveler is drawn. as if I had everything to say. I have said. Now the thought has come to me to write a complete story from the beginning of stories. Maybe this is the text of my writing that will form a bridge in the void.* Calvino's conversation with his reader at the beginning of each chapter brings the short circuit to its highest point: *You, the reader, are now ready to read the first lines of the first pages. Are you waiting to find the familiar tone of the author? Otherwise, you will not find it. Who said that this author has a familiar tone?*

1.5 Conclusions

A comparative and scrutinizing examination of different dimensions and angles of the novel *if on a winter's night a traveler* shows that there are obvious and similar postmodern components in it. The division based on which this research was analyzed is based on the postmodern components that are shown in the text of the novel as follows:

Deconstruction: The novel is not devoid of this characteristic and at the very beginning for the singer shows himself to be very dizzying and unconventional, which is based on different limitations and discrete narratives, but in an innovative way. The author continuously changes the content forms of each narrative based on its decentralization, but preserves their internal structures. By mentioning simple details in the form of his narratives, he has done an interesting deconstruction and keeps the reader in a state of suspense.

The metafictional layer: this component is revealed in the novel by the metafictional presence of the author and male reader, the author's remarks about how to read the novel and address the reader in the text, which continues until the end of the story, placing the reader's duty by searching for the original version of his novel. He gives and removes the limitations of the stories of his time and recognizes a new model based on the transformation of reality in story writing based on metafiction. The spy aspect, which is one of the characteristic sub-branches of metafiction, in the chapters without fear of height and wind and if a night of nights. and in the character of Marana the translator and Lotharia the sister of the reader of the novel, all of which are based on the fear of chaos and the insecurity of life. It is human, it is obvious.

In the novel, the reader enters a labyrinth of the fictional world and the real world, from which it seems very difficult to escape. In this story, the audience is constantly involved with the fictional world and its own real world, so that in one part, the narrator tells the audience about the woman in the story that it is because of your expectation that the author created this character in the story to make the story interesting. The conversation between the author and the reader from the very beginning of the story to the end breaks the boundaries between the real world and the fictional world and makes the reader understand that he is not dealing with an ordinary work.

Para-narrative: In the novel, the reader, from reading unfinished sub-narratives and the presence of various and centerless characters, finally realizes that he should not expect a single and coherent para-narrative and a knowledgeable narrator in this novel. Of course, the author attributes the absence of a general meta-narrative in this novel to a publishing mistake, the pleasures caused by the use of paperbacks, and even the presence of a fraudulent translator, so that the reader is not surprised to see partial narratives and prepares himself for reading each new narrative. In this novel, the multiplicity of half-finished narratives has caused the comprehensive and meaningful narration of the book, which is in the context of how to read and write a book and is related to the culture of every society, to collapse.

Short circuit: The author of the novel has also left a trace of himself in the form of each of the characters in the ten narratives of his novel in the form of a first-person narrator and has brought it to its peak. With an attractive beginning and in the ups and downs of his narratives, he walks through the pages of the book and establishes a connection with his reader and turns him from a passive audience to an active reader.

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Procedure for Pre-Judicial Settlement of Economic Disputes (Filing A Claim)

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Annotation: This research work is devoted to the analysis of the procedure for pre-trial settlement of economic disputes in the context of filing a claim. The main purpose of the work is to identify the procedural aspects and legal mechanisms that govern the process of filing a claim in economic disputes. The paper analyzes the legislation and judicial practice related to the pre-trial settlement of economic disputes, as well as examines scientific research related to this topic. As a result of the study, the main stages of the process of filing a claim are highlighted, including filing a claim, drafting and filing a claim, as well as the necessary formalities and deadlines that should be observed. Particular attention is paid to the procedure for filing a claim with the court, including the necessary documents that must be submitted to the court, and the requirements for the content of the statement of claim. It also discusses issues related to the determination of the competent court to consider economic disputes and the time frame during which it is necessary to file a claim. At the end of the work, conclusions are drawn about the importance of the correct observance of the procedure for filing a claim in economic disputes, since this is an important stage for ensuring the legality and efficiency of the consideration of disputes in court. Proper observance of the procedure allows you to protect the interests of the parties, ensure fair resolution of disputes and maintain legal stability in the economic sphere.

Key words: pre-trial settlement procedure, economic disputes, filing a claim, claim procedure, pre-trial settlement, filing a claim, legal procedure, defendant and plaintiff, evidence and arguments, judicial competence

Economic disputes arise in the sphere of business relations and can have serious consequences for the parties. An important aspect of resolving such disputes is the process of their pre-trial settlement. Filing a claim is the initial stage of this process, which determines its further course. In this article, we will consider the procedure for pre-trial settlement of economic disputes and the main points related to filing a claim.

Filing a claim is one of the most important moments in the pre-trial settlement of economic disputes. It allows you to initiate the dispute resolution process and is designed to ensure fairness and protection of the interests of the parties. Depending on the particular jurisdiction and the nature of the dispute, the procedure for filing a claim may vary slightly, but the general principles remain the same.

The first step in filing a claim is to file a claim. A statement of claim is a document in which the plaintiff presents his claims and demands against the defendant. The statement of claim must clearly state the facts of the case, provide evidence and provide references to the regulations governing the dispute. When preparing a statement of claim, it is important to contact a professional lawyer who will help draw up a document in accordance with the requirements of the law and protect the interests of the plaintiff as much as possible.

After drawing up the statement of claim, the plaintiff must file it with the competent court or arbitration court, depending on the specific situation and the agreements of the parties. Filing a claim is usually accompanied by the payment of a state fee or other fees that are charged for the consideration of the case. After the receipt of the statement of claim by the court or arbitration court, the process of considering the case begins.

The next step after filing a claim is the appointment of a court hearing. At the hearing, the parties present their arguments and evidence, act with the argumentation of their positions. The court considers the submitted materials and makes a decision. The decision of the court may be appealed on appeal, if the legislation provides for such a possibility.

It is important to note that filing a claim is only the beginning of the process of pre-trial settlement of economic disputes. In many cases, the parties may attempt to resolve the dispute out of court, for example, by negotiating or using alternative dispute resolution methods such as mediation or arbitration. Out-of-court settlement of disputes can be a more effective and faster way to reach an agreement between the parties, so it is worth considering such possibilities before filing a claim.

In conclusion, the procedure for pre-trial settlement of economic disputes begins with the filing of a claim. This stage is essential to start the dispute resolution process. Drawing up a correct statement of claim and its submission to the competent court or arbitration court are key points. However, before filing a claim, it is worth considering the possibilities of pre-trial settlement of the dispute in order to find the most effective way to resolve the conflict.

Pre-trial settlement of economic disputes is an important stage in the process of resolving conflicts arising in the sphere of economy and commerce. It is a way to achieve justice and protect the rights and interests of the parties without the involvement of the judiciary. In this article, we will consider the procedure for filing a claim in the pre-trial settlement of economic disputes.

1. Identification of the dispute and analysis of the legal basis: The first step in the pre-trial settlement of economic disputes is the identification of the conflict and the analysis of the legal basis. The parties must determine the essence of the dispute and identify the relevant rules of law that can be applied to resolve it. This may include an analysis of contracts, legislation or other regulatory documents that may be relevant to the dispute.

2. Filing a claim: After identifying the dispute, the party wishing to file a claim must prepare and file a claim against the opposing party. The claim requirement must be clear, specific and contain full information about the dispute, grounds and requirements. It must be signed and sent by mail, courier service or other means of communication that provide proof of its delivery.

3. Negotiation and mediation: After filing a claim, the parties can begin negotiations and attempts to resolve the dispute through interaction and search for a mutually beneficial solution. This process may involve a neutral intermediary or mediator to help the parties reach an agreement. Negotiation and mediation can help avoid litigation and reach a mutually beneficial agreement.

4. Arbitration and Alternative Dispute Resolution: In the event that negotiations and mediation fail to resolve the dispute, the parties may turn to arbitration or other alternative dispute resolution methods. Arbitration is the process of resolving a dispute with the help of an independent arbitration tribunal, which makes a binding decision for the parties. Alternative means of resolving disputes include the use of forensic expertise, expert advice or arbitration.

5. Filing a claim with the judicial authorities: If all attempts at pre-trial settlement have not yielded results, the parties may decide to file a claim with the judicial authorities. In doing so, all procedural requirements must be met, such as filing a claim, providing the necessary evidence and meeting deadlines. Litigation may require more time and resources than pre-trial settlement, but may ultimately lead to a final resolution of the dispute.

In conclusion, the procedure for pre-trial settlement of economic disputes is a sequence of steps, starting with the identification of the dispute and the analysis of the legal basis, and ending with the filing of a claim with the judicial authorities. It is important for the parties to actively engage in the settlement process and look for opportunities to reach a mutually beneficial agreement, thereby avoiding lengthy and costly litigation procedures.

In the economic sphere, disputes and disagreements arise between the parties related to the performance of contracts, settlements, the quality of goods and services, infringement of intellectual property rights and other issues. To resolve such disputes, most countries provide for a pre-trial settlement procedure, under which one of the parties can file a claim with the competent authority or court.

The procedure for pre-trial settlement of economic disputes usually begins with the filing of a claim. The lawsuit is a document in which the plaintiff sets out his claims against the defendant and demands the protection of his rights. Different jurisdictions may have specific requirements for the content and form of a claim, so it is important to familiarize yourself with the relevant rules or consult a lawyer for advice.

Before filing a claim, it is important to prepare in advance. This may include collecting the necessary evidence, analyzing legislation, assessing possible risks and consulting with legal experts. The purpose of such preparation is to ensure that the claim is valid and successful.

The main step in filing a claim is to file it with the competent authority or court. Depending on the country and the type of dispute, a claim may be filed with an arbitration court, an economic court, a civil court or a specialized court. It is important to determine the correct jurisdiction so that the claim is considered by the competent authority.

When filing a claim, you usually need to fill out the appropriate forms and provide the necessary documents. The claim must contain the identification data of the parties, the essence and grounds for claims, the requirements and justification for their legality. Evidence, such as contracts, invoices, correspondence and other documents that confirm the violation of the plaintiff's rights, can be an attachment to the claim.

After filing a claim, it is usually considered by the competent authority or court. In some cases, a preliminary hearing or negotiations between the parties may be scheduled to try to reach an amicable settlement of the dispute. If an amicable settlement is not reached, the case goes to trial.

At the stage of judicial consideration of an economic dispute, the parties present their arguments, present evidence and express their position. The court considers the evidence presented and applies the relevant legislation to reach a decision. The decision of the court may be challenged in higher instances, if it is provided by law.

It is important to note that the procedure for pre-trial settlement of economic disputes may differ in different countries and types of disputes. It may also be amended or supplemented by relevant legislation. Therefore, it is important to seek the advice of competent lawyers or legal professionals in order to stay up to date with the latest information and follow all necessary procedures when filing a claim.

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Methods of Administration and their Effects on Social Conflicts

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Annotation: This article examines different management methods and social conflicts. Sotsialnye conflicty yavlyayutsya neizbezhnoy chastyu obshchestvennoy zizni i mogut voznikat iz-za lichnykh prichin, such as racial, ethnic, political and economic differences. Conflict management plays an important role in supporting stability, harmony, and society. V state analiziruyutsya different management methods, including diplomatic, political, legal and social-economic approaches. Issledovanie pokazyvaet, chto vybor metoda upravleniya mojet imet znachitelnoe influence na character i dlitelnost sotsialnykh konfliktov. The article describes the effectiveness of any management method and ego performance and social conflicts. Nekotorye podkhody mogut sposobstvovat peaceful resolution of conflicts and sodeystvovat sotrudnichestvu and mutual understanding among different groups of society. Other methods may lead to increased tension and conflict.

Key words: management methods, social conflicts, conflict management, racial conflicts, ethnic conflicts, political conflicts, economic conflicts, diplomatic approach, political approach, legal approach, socio-economic approach, peaceful resolution of conflicts.

The management method can have a significant impact on social conflicts. There are several methods of management and social conflict:

1. **Demokraticeskoe upravlenie:** Prinyatie resheniy na osnoe consensusa i uchet mneniya razlichnykh interseptennykh storon mojet sposobstvovat razresheniyu konfliktov. Demokraticeskoe upravlenie obespechivaet uchastie grajdan v prinyatii resheniy i uchityvaet ix interesy. Eto mojet sposobstvovat snizeniyu dopolstva and prevention of social conflicts.

2. **Authoritarian management:** Authoritarian methods of management, characterized by the concentration of power in the hands of small groups, can lead to social conflicts. Ogranichenie svobody slova, prav i uchastiya grajdan mojet vyzyvat indolstvo i protesty, chto mojet privesti k sotsialnym conflictam.

3. **Konsultativnoe upravlenie:** This method of management presupposes three opinions of employees or other interested parties in making a decision. Konsultativnoe upravlenie mojet sposobstvovat snizeniyu tension i konfliktov, poskolku rabotniki chuvstvuyut sebya bolee vovlechennymi i uvajaemyi.

4. **Mediation:** Mediation is a conflict management method in which a neutral mediator helps the parties find a compromise solution. Mediation mojet pomoch smyagchit conflicty i dostich vzaimoponimaniya, pozvolyaya storonam vyrazit svoi interesy i obsudit vozmojnye reshenia.

5. **Empathy and mejkulturnoe ponimanie:** Upravlentsy, proyavlyayushchie empatiyu i imeyushchie horoshee mejkulturnoe ponimanie, mogut snizit veroyatnost sotsialnykh konfliktov. Umenie slushat i ponimat need i motivy drugikh lyudey pozvolyaet predotvratit noplststvo i raznoglasi.

The specific influence of management methods and social conflicts depends on the context, cultural characteristics and other factors. Otkrytyy dialog, vzaimnoe uvajenie i spravlidoe raspredelenie resursov yavlyayutsya klyuchevymi aspektami upravleniya, sposobstvuyushchimi snizeniyu sotsialnykh konfliktov.

Management and its methods can have a significant impact on social conflicts. Here are some methods of management and their possible impact on social conflicts: Dialogue and mediation: The use of dialogue and mediation can help resolve conflicts by ensuring open communication between the parties. This can help the parties to the conflict understand each other's positions, find common interests and work towards finding a compromise. Dialogue and mediation can alleviate tensions and help build trust between the parties, which can lead to a peaceful resolution of the conflict.

Political reforms: Reforms in the political sphere, such as improving the process of representation, expanding the rights and freedoms of citizens, can reduce social conflicts. When citizens have the opportunity

to express their opinions, participate in decision-making and see the results of their participation, this can reduce the feeling of inequality and injustice that can cause conflicts. Economic measures: Economic policies and measures can also influence social conflicts. Inequality in the distribution of resources, access to economic opportunities and working conditions can be a source of tension and conflict in society. The adoption of policies that reduce inequalities, improve access to education and health care, and create equal opportunities for all citizens can help reduce social conflict.

Judicial system: An efficient and fair judicial system can play an important role in resolving social conflicts. When citizens have confidence that their rights will be protected and that they will receive a fair trial, this can reduce the likelihood of violence and lynching. Guaranteeing legal protection and access to justice for all citizens can help reduce conflict and create a more stable society. Social inclusion and education: Social inclusion and education play an important role in preventing social conflicts. When all citizens have equal opportunities to receive education, access to information and resources, this can reduce inequality and increase social justice. Education also promotes critical thinking and empathy, which can help people understand each other better and find ways to cooperate instead of conflict.

All these control methods can interact and influence each other. The combination of these methods, adapted to the specific contexts and needs of society, can help prevent and resolve social conflicts, creating a more sustainable and harmonious society. The modern world is often faced with social conflicts that can cause tension and disruption of harmony in society. However, there are various management practices that can help prevent and resolve these conflicts. In this article, we will look at several key management practices and their impact on social conflicts, as well as the role they play in building peace and promoting cooperation. Dialogue and mediation: One of the most effective methods of resolving social conflicts is the use of dialogue and mediation. These tools allow parties to a conflict to communicate openly, express their opinions and interests, and seek common solutions. Dialogue and mediation contribute to the creation of an atmosphere of trust and mutual understanding, which in turn can lead to a reduction in tension and the search for a peaceful solution to the conflict.

Political reforms: One of the root sources of social conflict is the dissatisfaction of citizens with the political system and the lack of participation in decision-making. The introduction of political reforms, such as expanding the rights of citizens, improving the process of representation, and strengthening democratic institutions, can reduce social conflicts. When citizens see that their opinions are taken into account and their rights are protected, they are more likely to cooperate and participate in public life. Economic measures: Inequality in the distribution of resources and access to economic opportunities are notable sources of social conflict. Policies that reduce inequalities, create equal opportunities, and improve working conditions can help reduce conflict. Supporting economic development, investing in education and improving access to health services are key measures that can create a more just and equal society.

Judicial system: An efficient and fair judicial system plays an important role in resolving social conflicts. Citizens' confidence that their rights will be protected and that they will receive a fair trial can reduce tension and the likelihood of violence. The guarantee of legal protection and access to a fair trial for all citizens contributes to the creation of a peaceful society based on rights and law. Social inclusion and education: Social inclusion and education play an important role in preventing social conflicts. Ensuring equal educational opportunities, access to information and resources helps to reduce inequalities and increase social equity. Education promotes the development of critical thinking, empathy and understanding, which leads to better interaction between people and the search for ways of cooperation instead of conflict.

Social conflicts are an integral part of society. They arise from a variety of causes, including inequality, resource allocation, cultural differences, and political disputes. However, conflict management and application of appropriate methods can have a significant impact on the resolution of these conflicts and the creation of a more harmonious society.

One of the important methods of managing social conflicts is dialogue and mediation. This method includes the organization of open communication between the parties to the conflict in order to find compromise solutions. Dialogue and mediation allow the parties to the conflict to better understand each other's positions, identify common interests and find mutually beneficial solutions. In addition, these methods help reduce tension and restore trust between the parties, which can lead to a peaceful resolution of the conflict. In the political sphere, there are also management practices that can influence social conflicts. One such

method is the introduction of political reforms. Reforms aimed at improving the process of representation, expanding the rights and freedoms of citizens, can reduce social conflicts. When citizens feel that their voice is heard and taken into account in decision-making, it can reduce the sense of inequality and injustice that are the source of conflict.

Economic measures also play an important role in the management of social conflicts. Inequality in the distribution of resources and access to economic opportunities can be a source of social tension. Adopting policies that reduce inequalities, improve access to education and health care, and create equal opportunities for all citizens can help reduce social conflict. The judiciary also plays an important role in managing and resolving social conflicts. Ensuring an efficient and fair judicial system can reduce the likelihood of violence and lynching. When citizens have confidence in the legal system and are confident that their rights will be protected, this contributes to the peaceful resolution of conflicts.

Finally, social inclusion and education are integral parts of social conflict management methods. Education plays an important role in developing critical thinking, empathy and understanding of the differences between people. Increasing the availability of education and creating conditions for social inclusion help to reduce inequalities and contribute to the reduction of social conflicts.

In conclusion, methods of governance and their impact on social conflicts are necessary to create a harmonious society. The combined application of dialogue and mediation, political reforms, economic measures, the judiciary and social inclusion can help prevent and resolve social conflicts, creating a sustainable and just society where differences and disagreements are resolved peacefully.

Conclusion: Management practices play a key role in preventing and resolving social conflicts. The combination of dialogue and mediation, political reforms, economic measures, a fair judiciary and social inclusion help create a more sustainable and harmonious society. Through cooperation and taking into account the interests of all participants in the conflict, peace and justice can be achieved, which is an important factor in the development of prosperous and stable societies.

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Manager's Style and Image.

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Annotation: This article information about describes the activities of the manager, the difference between the manager and the leader, the behavior culture of the manager, the manager's image, and the advantages of leadership in the team.

Key words: Manager, leader, critical situations, organizational leader, management, leadership, manager's image, imageology.

In the years of independence, much attention is paid to the connection of each shrine with a human name, human factor, human intellect. In the field of culture and art, recognition of the human image, creativity and creativity in the best performance, the best festive event, the brightest film, the most beautiful work of art has been elevated to the state level policy. The introduction of creative exams in higher educational institutions in the field of culture and art, the introduction of the process of live performance without phonograms at government events, in turn, is a form of attitude and respect for the human factor organization and management of the artistic sphere, problems related to management activities, effective organization of the activities of other groups by individuals and groups of individuals, as well as a number of innovations are being introduced into the organizational structures of joint activities.

Problems of organization and management of cultural and artistic activities in philosophy, history, economics, jurisprudence and psychology is also closely related to problems.

In every organization, managers work alongside the leader, and in their place, leaders with a special reputation in the team also provide special services for the successful operation of the organization.

"Image" is an English word that means "image", "fame", introduction. As each person has his own "I", the "I" of managers is their image, that is, their business cards.

A certain uniqueness, a feature that stands out from others, a special definition represents the image of the manager.

The formation of the manager's image is manifested in interpersonal relations, in the ability to draw correct conclusions from difficult situations, in the ability to use anger and kindness in their place.

The organization will be blessed only when theory and practice work together. First of all, managers should pay attention to this.

At all times, the principle of respect and attention at work inspired employees and was clearly visible as a result of this work.

In many cases, the friendly relations of managers led to the elimination of conflicts, the prevention of bias and indifference, what difficult work can be entrusted to an employee, “difficult?”, “It is possible to the end”, “Who are you less?” phrases perform even the simplest task

may lead to a situation where you cannot receive it. Human mental processes, good or bad words heard from leaders can either make work boring or make them more interested in work. Experienced leaders understand well what a good word can do, and what consequences a bad word can bring. In other words, leaders accept the results they expect as a response to their relationship.

First of all, managers should pay attention to this.

The creation of a manager's image is known in different situations. According to experts, a person's appearance and manners give 90% of the value. That is why the most necessary qualities of well-known politicians and experienced managers can be seen in the following:

image makers are engaged in. They change the leaders' lifestyle, character, behavior, behavior, high mood, not to be nervous about everything in such a way that the leaders don't recognize themselves.

In this regard, in turn, managers, that is, leaders, help image makers to have fewer negative vices and more work-related qualities.

Only intellectuals who believe in themselves and their will deserve the respect and admiration of others, therefore, the attention and respect of employees allows to replenish and restore bioenergetic power.

For a leader, these aspects are important in shaping his image:

Put the sound freely;

- taking a bold step;

-not expressing inner mood;

the art of making a pleasant impression

1. Peace of mind first;
2. Business mood;
3. Not expressing emotion;
4. Being cold;

Calm-ness leads to effective listening to the problem of the employee who entered the reception, business mood - to "infect" other teammates, not to express emotions - not to approach the attitude of others to one's problem, to be cold - leads to boldness in solving the problem. That is why the working mood of the morning remains at the end of the working day.

And the verbal effect in the leader's activity reveals the icons of standing with feet together, moving hands in moderation, maintaining a moderate and calm tone of voice, and speaking fluently and expressively.

Why do you need an image?

- only the image helps to get into an easy relationship with the employees;
- to hide personal negative habits of the leader;
- to hide appearance defects;
- to hide professional skills, service etiquette.

As we know from management, there are two types of people-pleasing:

- method of persuasion;
- burning method.

Another influence technology of liking people is called imagiology. What can "infect" a person with others is their attractiveness and sharing a bright mood. There is another component that cannot be left out of the culture of business, business, team behavior, attitude culture, and this is the manager's appearance, clothes. The appearance is also extremely should be compact and attractive. It is advisable for a female manager to wear only two colors. Black suit, black skirt or black pants, black bag, black or white shoes.

The second outfit is a beautiful blouse, a fashionable skirt or a light-colored women's shirt. Evening wear is a dress and shirt-suit that comes below the knee. Hairstyle, shoes, bag and jewelry are additional decorations (attributes).

There are three types of suits for male managers: business suits, business suits for evening negotiations. Ties match the color of suits. Service suits - simple suit and pants; Evening - suits and trousers of the same color, according to fashion; Business suits - the latest style. Ties, watches, shoes, vests, scarves, shoes are also chosen in the colors of the suits. These recommendations, recommended by experts, are a time-tested example of business and simplicity in managerial activities. In addition, the golden rule for managers is: they are welcomed by clothes, they observe according to the mind.

- Fulfill this promise on time, keep your word under any circumstances
- Being unbiased and objective about "useless" suggestions that lead to wasted time
- Politely and politely reject offers that are not useful to him and his team
- To be self-confident in any round or event, avoid big departures
- As a leader, do not discourage subordinates, educate them properly, encourage their productive work and initiative
- Not to be individualistic, not to forget that one's opinion and point of view are not always correct, that there are other opinions and points of view that are not completely bad
- Thorough analysis of operational failures, outages and errors
- Among the employees, curbing anger, not losing patience

The activity of the manager is especially important in the development of the system of organization and management of culture and art.

Talented leaders are actively working in theaters, houses of culture, museums, libraries, children's music and art schools, creative teams, which creates the basis for bright reforms in the development of these areas.

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Issues of Nation and Spirituality in the Poems of Abdulla Qadiri. A Decision to My Nation and An Example of Opinion Poems

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Annotation: In this article, the unique features of Abdulla Qadiri's views on Jadidism were written, and the poems of Abdulla Qadiri such as "Tuy", "Ahvolimiz" are artistically analyzed. Also, the article clearly reflects Abdulla Qadiri's ability to use words in poetic verses.

Key Words: Qadiri's lyrics, skill of using words, independence singer, poetic expression, national value.

There are many works of Abdulla Qadiri dedicated to the development of the nation and homeland. Even so, among them, Abdulla Qadiri's poems such as "A decision for my nation" and "Fikr Aylagil" are unique with their artistry, form of expression and content. The double reading of these poems has a good effect on the reader and creates alertness in the reader. The beginning of the poem "A decision for my nation" with the same urge as "Kel ey millat" expresses a unique spirit of invitation. In the verses of the poem, he expresses the need to rely on science in order to unite forces for the development of the country.

"According to our observation, Abdulla Qadiri's work began in 1913-1914, and for the first time, articles, opinions and comments about him appeared in the September 23, 1915 issue of the newspaper "Turkestanskije vedomosti".[1] Abdulla Qadiri's eloquence makes him unique with his ability to infuse many nuances of meaning into short words. According to Qadiri, people's ignorant decisions are likened to the fact that winter always prevails and the race is divided into four seasons. That's why, while trying to get rid of ignorance, he emphasizes that it is necessary to dry ignorance in the desert while keeping the courage high. When talking about the progress of our society if the country develops, it is explained by the fact that the rich should make a big contribution to these actions. Abdulla Qadiri once again mentions the same thoughts as many of his contemporaries. In this place, through the phrase "Salib dorilfunul, makotib hazan olsun", the concept that everyone should be at the same step in the implementation of various reforms is put forward. It goes without saying that the representatives of the intelligentsia and the rich should take part in these actions. Here he says about future generations:

"May the generation of the nation pray for us always,
Good luck to those who are studying.
Let's cry together, let's cry a lot for graces,
So that the orphan and the poor may die as a maid."

From the above-mentioned poetic lines, it is understood that the education of the youth, who are the future of the nation, is more necessary than ever, and it is concluded that the generation of the nation prays after such works and the contribution of people to the development of the nation. Abdulla Qadiri's definition of ignorance and lack of enlightenment also shows that his skill in using words is at a high level. In this regard, he describes the continuing state of ignorance as "the scum of ignorance." The continued existence of ignorance is shown to be the main cause of people's ignorance, and the people who caused you to be victims of ignorance are happy about it and say, "our coming out of ignorance hurts them" - Abdulla Qadiri in his poems. In his poem "Fikr Aylagil", Abdulla Qadiri regrets that the money earned for the needs of daily life is not used for science and enlightenment. The main factor of Bulae is injustice, ignorance, sale of land for weddings and shows, waste of money is described as one of the signs of ignorance. In his poem, he criticizes the relations of the rich and the statesmen with the owners and merchants, noting that their relations with the people of knowledge are not strong, but on the contrary, he criticizes their opposition to the supporters of innovation.

"In classical literary studies, the art of expressing many meanings with few words is called "Iyjaz". The evocative status of the word is characteristic of the poetics of Abdullah Qadiri's prose and the speech of his heroes".[2] In Absulla Qadiri's poem "Fikr Aylagil", our wives and daughters have gold and jewels

around their necks, but regretting that they have little understanding of science and enlightenment, they eagerly begin to think and learn. At the end of the poem, Abdulla Qadiri is portrayed as a passer-by who talks about his troubles and sorrows and asks them not to blame him for such thoughts. Abdulla Qadiri reminds the people of the country to think about the above-mentioned ideas in this regard. That is why it is important that the name of the poem is taken as a thought.

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The Role of Ethnic Culture in Formation of Ideological Immunity in the Youth

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Annotation. The article examines the internal, immanent features of Uzbek ethnoculture, aspects related to the national idea. The national ideological and ideological essence of artistic and aesthetic images and images in Uzbek ethnoculture is revealed. Forming an aesthetic ideal is the main function of Uzbek ethnoculture. In the article, the features of this function, issues of wider use of ethnocultural possibilities for its formation are studied from the point of view of national idea and ideology.

Keywords: *Uzbek, ethnoculture, national idea, ideology, aesthetic ideal, ideological immunity, youth, artistic-aesthetic*

Introduction

In the words of the well-known art critic and philosopher M.S. Kagan, "from the intuitive perception of the whole to the theoretical understanding that it is a very complex and multifunctional system" [1; -p.9] there is a need for transition, without such an approach, it is impossible to stop the spread of conflicting, and sometimes completely incorrect, unrealistic, unscientific views about material culture and spiritual culture, civilization and culture, types, manifestations, and architecture of cultural activities. "What is culture?" The epistemological question requires axiological differentiation of "true culture" from "false culture". Such a distinction, in turn, answers the question "what kind of culture should be and how will it be?". These questions are not the product of epistemological research, fantasy games, and purely metaphysical observations. Human development, "clash of civilizations", national, religious, ideological and social conflicts arising in different regions make it necessary to positively solve the issue of culture. It is also an axiom that only culture can save humanity from destruction, destructive wars, and conflicts [1; -S.13]. It is for this reason that the search for ways to effectively use the positive experiences in the morals, manners, customs, traditions, works, oral and written works created by the people, in short, the national culture (ethnoculture) is a requirement of social development, an objective necessity.

Materials and methods

Foreign scientists G. Gadamer, K. Lévi-Strauss, A. Toynbee, Y. Heizinga, O. Spengler, primitive ideas, customs, way of life, stages of formation of consciousness, creation of labor tools, language, socio-historical processes, ethics, who researched some ethnocultural processes related to society and development. Their scientific conclusions serve as a theoretical basis for the study and objective assessment of ethnocultures. At the same time, in them, on the one hand, some empirical materials, ethnocultural processes are presented as a criterion applicable to all mankind, and on this basis, a desire to draw a global conclusion, on the other hand, to abstract the subject, to interpret subjective opinion as a single scientific truth is visible. A holistic approach to ethnoculture requires ensuring coherence of subjective opinion with empirical material.

CIS scientists L.N. Gumilyov, S.N. Ikonnikova, M.S. Kagan, L.N. Kogan, D.S. Likhachev, M.O. Shavaeva conducted research in various directions related to the topic. L. N. Gumilyov's research on the role of ancient Turkic tribes in the formation of Eurasian civilization stands out from the others.

Among Uzbek scientists, U. Karaboev analyzed Uzbek ethnoculture in connection with rituals and holidays, traditional games, folk entertainment, folk medicine, folk art, folk pedagogy (ethnopedagogy), folk applied art, national costumes and dressing culture, ecology and the development of folk household culture. . He emphasizes that ethnoculture is a reality related to science, enlightenment, religion, literature, art, creativity, folk traditions, and all spheres of human life [2]. U. Mengligulov studied the ethnoculture of the

Surkhan oasis, tried to preserve the national identity in the multi-ethnic area, reveal the socio-cultural aspects of the ethnocultural traditions [3].

F. Atamuratova, U. Otanova and G. Shodimetova's researches promoting the integral connection of Uzbek culture with the spiritual culture and the processes of forming a perfect generation during the years of independence were expressed. In particular, U. Otanova categorizes folk culture into socio-economic, agricultural, urban life, politics, society and state management, democracy, enlightenment and education, education, household life, literature and art, amateur creativity [4]. The researcher comes to the conclusion that as long as a person, a nation, a people exist, their characteristic ethno-cultural signs will not disappear.

Main part

Ethnoculture is the result of a person's subjective activity aimed at epistemological understanding of the world, social existence. This subjective basis of ethnoculture comes as an expression of certain ideas and ideology in material and spiritual wealth. Even weapons and artifacts aimed at utilitarian purposes carry not only aesthetic, but also social, economic, and even political views and thoughts of the subject. It should be noted that the purpose of Uzbek hat is not only to protect the head from heat and cold, but also it has become a symbol of national pride and national identity. It is possible to distinguish representatives of existing ethnic groups in society by their appearance, local-ethnographic signs, clothing culture, and even kinesics and gestural behavior. This is not only the effect of physiological, biological, but also "cultural determinism" [5]. This influence creates certain stereotypes in mentality, behavior, and relationships. By studying this situation, following the "template", we know to which ethnicity and ethnoculture a person belongs, by analyzing his clothes, kinesics, aesthetic taste, and what social ideas he is a supporter of. It is true that we may be mistaken in these ideas, but we will not stop striving to know and understand a person's inner world, ethnoculture, and aesthetic taste from stereotypes. Especially when a person directs his actions to create something, he "spends" his inner thoughts, ideas and views, aesthetic taste on that thing. In this way, the objectification of consciousness and taste occurs.

Uzbek ethnoculture has not always had a national idea and ideology in the current sense. Some researchers derive the roots of the national idea and ideology from the culture of antiquity, from our ancient narratives. In our opinion, in earlier societies, the national idea and ideology did not exist as a theoretical-philosophical concept as it is now, but in the form of ideas, approaches, and goals that led to the formation of Uzbek and other peoples of our country in the form of social unity. Although the national idea and ideology turned into a theoretical-philosophical concept, a recognized doctrine with the full formation of the Uzbek nation, it has always existed within the Uzbek ethnoculture as a component of it. Therefore, it is a mistake to separate ethnoculture from the national idea and ideology, to build a "Chinese wall" between them.

Ethnoculture is essentially related to the national idea and ideology. Thoughts, ideas, goals for which the hero fought, images, lines, even colors in patterns, their use, technology inform about national spirituality. Heart-warming, mournful melodies in Uzbek music, ibo in the movements of the dancers, elegance, gentleness, and even submissive meekness indicate the influence of social ideas, aesthetic views, in short, ideological factors in the ethno-aesthetic heritage of our people.

The national idea and ideology should make the nation a nation and the nation a nation. Uzbek ethnocultural heritage consistently describes the aspirations of our people to realize and preserve their identity. First of all, this is manifested in works of folk art and creativity depicting the struggle for the freedom of the Motherland and the people. The main heroes of folk epics such as "Alpomish", "Kirkkiz", "Gurugli", "Yodgorkhan", "Rustamkhan" are characters who instilled the feeling of patriotism in their hearts. In particular, Gurugli unites representatives of different peoples, gathers them around him, and opposes the enemies of his homeland. When he "grew up and became an adult, he became a mediator connecting blue and earth, more precisely, a savior who repels the evil forces that invade and threaten the people of the earth. He guided people and started them on the right path. He will establish justice in the derailed society and spread enlightenment" [6].

The struggles for the freedom and independence of the country and the people depicted in the folk books and epics are exaggerated and hyperbolic, the main character or a group of wrestlers fights with an entire army of enemies and ultimately defeats them. This artistic image inspires admiration, but does not forget how the heroes of the people are fighting against the evil and brutal force. Such a force can be defeated and crushed

only by a stronger and more powerful force, a hero who has the freedom of his country and people in his heart. Bringing the main characters as extremely strong, powerful, who single-handedly digs a ditch in the mountain and carries water, stands "against thousands of armies", "works day and night", "covers a distance of forty days in one moment" is a social, artistic and aesthetic image of the people. according to the ideal. The people inculcates their ideological, cultural and aesthetic views on the main characters, their struggle for the freedom of the homeland and the people.

These ethno-cultural and ethno-aesthetic features of the idea of freedom of the homeland and the people were transferred to the national idea and ideology formed during the years of independence. That is why experts interpret the idea of patriotism by connecting it with the historical feats of our ancestors, images, images, motives created in ethnoculture, especially in folklore, epics and songs, in short, exemplary plots and works that instill national pride and patriotism in the representatives of the nation and young people. Because the social ideas embedded in the works of the people create impressive and emotional images with the help of artistic and aesthetic means, they quickly and effectively affect people's minds, moods, and relationships. "The fact that in the past there were people like Shiroq, Spitamen, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, who were ready to sacrifice their lives for the protection of the Motherland and the peace of the country, strengthens people's confidence in the future" [7; -B. 152-153]. Based on this theoretical-philosophical concept, researchers define patriotism in the national idea and ideology:

- "- knowing the history of one's people well and being proud of it;
- preserving the material and spiritual heritage created by the great ancestors like the apple of an eye and passing it on to future generations;
- to study the traditions, customs and traditions of ancestors, and to continue the valuable part of it;
- means the future of our country, stability of independence, sincere feeling of the greatness of the future, earnestly helping to build such a future" [7; -B.153] they argue.

Uzbek national culture was formed on the basis of its core. Therefore, the Uzbek ethnoculture and its fundamentally important ideas, values, views are the root of today's national idea and ideology. Therefore, it is necessary to look for the fundamental values and conceptual views expressed in the content of the national idea and ideology from ethnoculture, ethnocultural and ethno-aesthetic heritage.

"A person always feels the need for a certain idea in relation to his life activity, society, state, and the people around him. Consequently, a person accepts thoughts that meet his needs. However, it is worth noting that these ideas cannot be outside the moral, political, artistic, aesthetic standards established in society. In order for an idea to serve the life and development of a person, first of all, it must represent the interests of the people, the nation, which is its subject and consumer, and reflect its moral needs" [8; -B.95]. Here we are talking about the moral and spiritual heritage and values that are unique to the Uzbek people, deeply embedded in their ethno-culture. Therefore, the main goal of the national idea and ideology is to satisfy the moral and spiritual needs of society and man [8; -B. 38].

Ethical and spiritual values are in the central place in Uzbek ethnoculture. In the struggle between goodness and evil, greatness and baseness, nobility and inferiority, ambivalent, antagonistic phenomena such as elegance and rudeness, the high moral and spiritual qualities that express the ideal of the people prevail and win. It is almost rare to celebrate such immoral events and traits as evil, baseness, meanness, and rudeness in folk creativity and art. It should be noted that in some episodes they are superior to high moral and spiritual qualities, positive, they make the protagonists sad, they are exposed to danger, ignorance, arrogance, but the hero of the people overcomes them through noble and beautiful goals and actions. .

"National idea, ethnic roots, history, culture, motherland, faith, spirituality, economic life, values, traditions and customs, is a spiritual factor that unites people of the same blood and soul in the path of specific goals and interests, common activities and directs them" [9]. The nature of the national idea, which unites ethnic groups and peoples to specific, strategic goals, is reflected in the integration, commonalities and commonalities of the ethno-culture.

In the Uzbek ethnocultural and ethno-aesthetic heritage, special attention is paid to the depiction of a person, his beautiful, noble qualities, love and affection for his relatives and others. Man, his beautiful and noble spirituality, inner world has not escaped the attention of subjects of folk creativity and art. The main goal of Uzbek ethnoculture was to depict a perfect person, to create a spiritually mature generation. Because,

"The idea of a perfect person is a noble idea that has both a national and a universal essence, embodies the highest spiritual and physical perfection of a human being, and always motivates him to be good.

This idea led not only individuals, but entire nations to high development, inspired them to unparalleled achievements in spirituality and enlightenment" [7; 56 pp.].

In the ethnocultural and ethnoaesthetic heritage, the nationality of the heroes is rarely mentioned. For folk creativity and art, a person, his spiritual and moral qualities, beautiful behavior are important. This universal approach does not reject the ethnic and national symbols in folk creativity and art, but indicates their harmony with universal values. None of the heroes of the people puts their ethnic origin above the ethnic characteristics of others, does not indulge in ethnocentric sentiments, does not promote the idea of nationalism. For them, ethnicity means serving the Motherland, the people, and protecting their interests. This means that the creation and art of the people originates from universal human goals, that its genesis lies in the goal of glorifying man, turning him into a creative, creative subject.

Conclusion

The ideogenesis of Uzbek ethnoculture (origin, basis of aesthetic views) is not aimed at supporting the ideas, interests and interests of narrow, class or certain groups. He is alien to classism, sectarianism, even raising his views to the level of dogma and forcing other ethnic groups to accept him. Neither the Uzbek people nor their ethnoculture tried to assimilate other peoples, they did not forcibly introduce their heritage, values, and concepts into different ethnocultures. Its characteristic tolerance allowed free use of existing artistic-aesthetic methods and images. Therefore, motifs, plots, styles, expressions and compositions characteristic of the cultures of Greek, Iranian, Arab, Mongolian, and Russian peoples can be found in the Uzbek ethnocultural and ethnoaesthetic heritage. At the same time, it cannot be said that the themes and pictorial styles encountered in ideogenesis did not enter. The material and spiritual wealth, artistic and aesthetic experiences acquired by the nation have been transferred from its historical-cultural paradigm, synthesis of ideological and spiritual values. This did not allow foreign, destructive, non-national views, invitations and experiences to enter the Uzbek ethnoculture. So, the ideological immunity we mean now is a gradual continuation of traditions and experiences in our ethnoculture.

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Interpretation of the emergence of a state in natural law theory

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Annotation. The article analyzes the causes and differences between theories of the origin of the state, the natural-law interpretation of the formation of the state from a scientific and theoretical point of view.

Keywords. The state, the emergence of the state, theories of the emergence of the state, the theory of natural law, the views of thinkers on the formation of the state.

The phenomena of the state and law are complex and have gone through a long path of gradual development. They arose at a certain stage of human society. In the history of mankind, there have been long periods without the state and law. People have been living on the basis of various associations - clan, tribe, tribe union. Nevertheless, it sufficiently ensured the rule of peace, tranquility and justice among people.

The state and law are the most valuable phenomena discovered by mankind, and the formation of the state laid the foundation for the full manifestation of man. The long periods from the emergence of the state and law to the present have led to the diversity of views and opinions about the emergence and essence of these phenomena. Until today, various theories explaining the process of creation and development of the state and law have been applied, and new theories are emerging.

Different interpretations of the emergence and development of the phenomena of the state and law are determined by the following: first, the process of the emergence of the state and law is complex and diverse; secondly, it is related to researchers' thinking, beliefs, interests and other subjective factors; thirdly, the presence of distortions of the issue of the initial emergence of the state and law based on one or another point of view; fourthly, the length of time that has passed since the state and law came into being, the fact that factual materials have not been preserved [1; P.30.]. The study of the process of formation of the state and law is not only of theoretical importance, but also of political and practical importance. It serves to deepen the understanding of the social nature of the state and law, their essence, their characteristics and signs. It helps to clearly define all the functions characteristic of them, to further clarify their place and importance in the life of society.

In the literature of jurisprudence, it is emphasized that the process of the creation of the state and the law itself are different. Firstly, it is necessary to distinguish the process of the first appearance of the state and law in the life of society. It is necessary to separate the formation process of state and legal phenomena, institutions and institutions based on the decay of state and legal phenomena, institutions and institutions that prevailed in this society [2; P.3].

Secondly, it is necessary to distinguish the process of formation and development of new state-legal case, institutions and organizations on the basis of the state-legal phenomena, institutions and organizations that were applied before but left the socio-political scene for some reasons [1; P.30].

Each of the states that came into being in ancient times went through a unique process in its own way. Despite this, scholars have lodged different theories based on the generalization of many recurring aspects in the formation of states. The most subjective notion is allowed in the interpretation of the process of origin of the state and law. Russian scientist G. F. Shershenevich explains the reason why there are many theories explaining the emergence of the state and law. According to him, for individual scientists, it is not important how the state actually arose, but rather how to find the way of the state's emergence, which is necessary to justify the preconceived idea is important [3; P.250].

The well-known political scientist L. Gumplovich draws attention to this situation and emphasizes the following: if the concept of the state usually served as a flag for expressing political tendencies, describing political programs and achieving a political goal, the same distortions were allowed in the historical issue of the creation of the state. In many cases, it was interpreted in a distorted way in the path of "superior ideas".

The pure issue of the formation of the state was built on a certain idea, explained based on certain needs, in other words, explained based on certain practical and moral motives. According to their interpretation, in order to preserve morality and human dignity, it is necessary to hide the true, natural origin of the state, and instead to present some legal and humane doctrine acceptable to many [4; P.47].

In the legal literature, it is recognized that in Ancient Greece, Egypt, Rome, and other countries, the first state-legal systems were created on the basis of the division of society into slaves and slaveholders, while in Central Asia and Russia, the system of slavery literally did not exist, and the state and law were formed based on common land ownership.

The emergence of the state and law largely depended on the natural conditions, climate, soil, water, and the proximity or distance of the territory to water basins, which had a direct impact on the formation of the system of people's lifestyle, outlook and needs. At the same time, each generation inherits a rich heritage from the past ancestors and leaves certain lessons for future generations. In this way, the future will greatly influence the development of social life.

Notions about the formation of the state and law were also put forward by supporters of the theory of natural law. The theory of natural law, which is very common in scientific literature, is one of the theories that arose in ancient times. The formation of the theory of natural law and its development is related to the activity and creativity of ancient Greek, Roman and Chinese thinkers [5; P.25-29].

Specific rules of this theory were developed by the sophists who worked in Ancient Greece in the V-IV centuries BC. According to the Sophists, human beings lived without any rules from the beginning, but later they were forced to develop different rules to ensure their safety and to live together.

According to the ancient Greek philosophers as Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle, not all laws are strictly man-made. In addition to the laws established by humans, "there are also divine laws that reside in the hearts of people. "In other words, in addition to the laws created depending on the will of man, that is, the laws issued by the state, there are also laws that do not depend on the will of man, and they are natural law. Based on these laws, an eternal, indivisible divine order reigns, and they are not only human relations between, but also "regulates the creation of the whole world" [2; P.49-63].

According to Aristotle, the state exists by nature and is by nature primary to every human being. Nature has placed in all people the desire to strive for the union of the state. First, whoever founded this association, he rendered unparalleled service to people [6; P.379].

The state is a product of natural development. In this respect, it is similar to the primary association of people, such as the family and the village. The union of a man and a woman to produce offspring creates a family. The increase of families creates villages, and the increase of villages creates the state. The ancient Greek philosopher Epicurus (341-270 BC) advocated the theory of natural law. In his opinion, nature develops according to its own laws, without the intervention of God. Justice, by its very nature, is a contract for benefit, not to harm each other and not to be harmed.

The ancient Greek historian Polybius (BC 210-123) describes the emergence of statehood and the change of state forms as a natural process that takes place according to the laws of nature. The creation of the human community is due to the natural weakness inherent in all living beings, which leads both animals and humans to unite into a single herd. Natural legal doctrines are reflected in the works of ancient Roman jurists and philosophers. According to Roman jurists, Roman law consists of *ius civil* (ancient Roman law that only regulates relations between Roman citizens), *ius gentium* (law that regulates property relations between Roman citizens and other peoples), and *ius natural-natural* law. Like the ancient Greeks, the Romans divided law into positive law, natural law, and divine law.

At all stages of the development of Roman law, according to Roman jurists, there was a difference in the essence of natural law and its relations common to all nations. Some Roman jurists distinguished them. Some saw them as equals. But almost all Roman jurists, unlike the ancient Greek jurists and philosophers, focused their attention on the conflict between positive law and natural law in a number of cases. One of the contradictions between natural law and positive law is that in natural law, all people are equal in law, there should be no difference between them according to their class and other social characteristics, and positive law is formed on the basis of those differences.

According to Zeno (336-264 BC), the founder of Stoicism, natural law is divine and has the power to command truth and forbid injustice. Stoics emphasize that civil society is based on the natural desire of people

towards each other, their natural relations. Accordingly, the state is not an artificial, conditional, contractual association, but a natural association.

Based on the idea of the unity of the divine and human worlds of the Roman Stoics, the Roman philosopher and statesman Seneca believed that people are related by blood and are parts of a single body. He believed that nature created all people from the same substance for the same purpose. The Supreme Bliss is the consciousness that is the divine soul placed in the human body. Consciousness makes man like God. In addition to consciousness, nature has given man the ability to join a community based on the unity of the human race. Thanks to consciousness and communication, humans outstripped animals in the struggle for survival, subjugated natural phenomena, and began to live as close communities.

The universe, according to Seneca, is a natural state in its own right, recognition of which is a necessary and conscious act. All human beings are members of this state by natural law, regardless of whether they recognize it or not. Separate state structures are important only for a limited number of people, not for the entire humanity.

The Roman jurist M. T. Cicero believes that the reason for the creation of the state is not only the weakness of people, but also their desire to live together. Based on Aristotle's teachings, Cicero emphasizes the importance of the family in the emergence of the state [7; P.21].

State and law are divine in their nature and essence and are based on common sense and justice. Studying all of nature leads to the realization that the world is ruled by consciousness. Humans are naturally embodied in consciousness and justice, and because of this, they can acquire divine foundations, the origin of ordered human society, virtue, state and law.

Hugo Grotius and Spinoza in Holland, Thomas Hobbes and John Locke in England, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, Paul Holbach in France, Alexander Radishev in Russia and others made their due contributions to the development of the theory of natural law.

According to Hugo Grotius, one of the founders of the school of natural law, human nature is the mother of natural law. Natural law means giving people what they already own and fulfilling the obligations imposed on them. Truth (justice) is compliance with the norms of natural law. Natural law does not depend on anyone because it is not the product of anyone's will [8; P.18].

He created the theoretical basis of the revolutionary movement in France and gave it an ideological basis. Jean Jacques Rousseau (1712-1778) brought the doctrine of natural law to its logical conclusion. Jean-Jacques Rousseau, comparing the theory of natural law with the reality of the environment, strongly condemned the regime of that time. Man by nature, writes Rousseau, is born free and free, but we now see their rights chained together. By nature, all men are related to each other by blood, but everywhere we see such differences between different strata, groups and classes, according to Rousseau, is the struggle for wealth. The main reason for such problems faced by people is ownership of private property and inequality [9; P.124-125].

In modern natural legal doctrines, special attention is paid to the issue of the emergence of the state. According to him, before explaining the emergence of the state, it is important to determine which category and group the state belongs to. The state is created on the basis of human associations or society. Some of them arose naturally (for example, family, clan, tribe), and some artificially (business association, religious associations, etc.). In the creation of the state, only the natural associations that formed it are taken into account.

O.R.Sulaymanov, one of the international scholars from Uzbekistan, admits that natural, inalienable human rights are constitutionally and internationally enshrined in the legal systems of many countries [11; P.45-50].

The most important difference between societies that exist separately or independently and societies that are part of higher associations is that individual associations are absorbed into and become part of higher associations, thus ceasing to function independently. This process continues naturally from the early stages of human society. Thus, according to Aristotle, the natural emergence of the state takes place. It can be seen that the modern theory of natural law has not moved away from its ideological basis. In general, natural law is the starting point of any law, therefore of legal order, positive law, moral law, political law and other forms of such rights.

Thus, society is an association of people interconnected by a certain system of relations, which was created before the state and law. The state as a complex socio-political phenomenon has traveled a long way of development. The emergence, formation and development of the state is covered based on different approaches. It is important to study both their positive and negative aspects without making one or another approach absolute.

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The state is a product of natural development. In this respect, it is similar to the primary association of people, such as the family and the village. The union of a man and a woman to produce offspring creates a family. The increase of families creates villages, and the increase of villages creates the state. The ancient Greek philosopher Epicurus (341-270 BC) advocated the theory of natural law. In his opinion, nature develops according to its own laws, without the intervention of God. Justice, by its very nature, is a contract for benefit, not to harm each other and not to be harmed.

The ancient Greek historian Polybius (BC 210-123) describes the emergence of statehood and the change of state forms as a natural process that takes place according to the laws of nature. The creation of the human community is due to the natural weakness inherent in all living beings, which leads both animals and humans to unite into a single herd. Natural legal doctrines are reflected in the works of ancient Roman jurists and philosophers. According to Roman jurists, Roman law consists of *ius civile* (ancient Roman law that only regulates relations between Roman citizens), *ius gentium* (law that regulates property relations between Roman citizens and other peoples), and *ius natural-natural law*. Like the ancient Greeks, the Romans divided law into positive law, natural law, and divine law.

At all stages of the development of Roman law, according to Roman jurists, there was a difference in the essence of natural law and its relations common to all nations. Some Roman jurists distinguished them. Some saw them as equals. But almost all Roman jurists, unlike the ancient Greek jurists and philosophers, focused their attention on the conflict between positive law and natural law in a number of cases. One of the contradictions between natural law and positive law is that in natural law, all people are equal in law, there should be no difference between them according to their class and other social characteristics, and positive law is formed on the basis of those differences.

According to Zeno (336-264 BC), the founder of Stoicism, natural law is divine and has the power to command truth and forbid injustice. Stoics emphasize that civil society is based on the natural desire of people

towards each other, their natural relations. Accordingly, the state is not an artificial, conditional, contractual association, but a natural association.

Based on the idea of the unity of the divine and human worlds of the Roman Stoics, the Roman philosopher and statesman Seneca believed that people are related by blood and are parts of a single body. He believed that nature created all people from the same substance for the same purpose. The Supreme Bliss is the consciousness that is the divine soul placed in the human body. Consciousness makes man like God. In addition to consciousness, nature has given man the ability to join a community based on the unity of the human race. Thanks to consciousness and communication, humans outstripped animals in the struggle for survival, subjugated natural phenomena, and began to live as close communities.

The universe, according to Seneca, is a natural state in its own right, recognition of which is a necessary and conscious act. All human beings are members of this state by natural law, regardless of whether they recognize it or not. Separate state structures are important only for a limited number of people, not for the entire humanity.

The Roman jurist M. T. Cicero believes that the reason for the creation of the state is not only the weakness of people, but also their desire to live together. Based on Aristotle's teachings, Cicero emphasizes the importance of the family in the emergence of the state [7; P.21].

State and law are divine in their nature and essence and are based on common sense and justice. Studying all of nature leads to the realization that the world is ruled by consciousness. Humans are naturally embodied in consciousness and justice, and because of this, they can acquire divine foundations, the origin of ordered human society, virtue, state and law.

Hugo Grotius and Spinoza in Holland, Thomas Hobbes and John Locke in England, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, Paul Holbach in France, Alexander Radishev in Russia and others made their due contributions to the development of the theory of natural law.

According to Hugo Grotius, one of the founders of the school of natural law, human nature is the mother of natural law. Natural law means giving people what they already own and fulfilling the obligations imposed on them. Truth (justice) is compliance with the norms of natural law. Natural law does not depend on anyone because it is not the product of anyone's will [8; P.18].

He created the theoretical basis of the revolutionary movement in France and gave it an ideological basis. Jean Jacques Rousseau (1712-1778) brought the doctrine of natural law to its logical conclusion. Jean-Jacques Rousseau, comparing the theory of natural law with the reality of the environment, strongly condemned the regime of that time. Man by nature, writes Rousseau, is born free and free, but we now see their rights chained together. By nature, all men are related to each other by blood, but everywhere we see such differences between different strata, groups and classes, according to Rousseau, is the struggle for wealth. The main reason for such problems faced by people is ownership of private property and inequality [9; P.124-125].

In modern natural legal doctrines, special attention is paid to the issue of the emergence of the state. According to him, before explaining the emergence of the state, it is important to determine which category and group the state belongs to. The state is created on the basis of human associations or society. Some of them arose naturally (for example, family, clan, tribe), and some artificially (business association, religious associations, etc.). In the creation of the state, only the natural associations that formed it are taken into account.

O.R.Sulaymanov, one of the international scholars from Uzbekistan, admits that natural, inalienable human rights are constitutionally and internationally enshrined in the legal systems of many countries [11; P.45-50].

The most important difference between societies that exist separately or independently and societies that are part of higher associations is that individual associations are absorbed into and become part of higher associations, thus ceasing to function independently. This process continues naturally from the early stages of human society. Thus, according to Aristotle, the natural emergence of the state takes place. It can be seen that the modern theory of natural law has not moved away from its ideological basis. In general, natural law is the starting point of any law, therefore of legal order, positive law, moral law, political law and other forms of such rights.

Thus, society is an association of people interconnected by a certain system of relations, which was created before the state and law. The state as a complex socio-political phenomenon has traveled a long way of development. The emergence, formation and development of the state is covered based on different approaches. It is important to study both their positive and negative aspects without making one or another approach absolute.

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Evaluation of a training curriculum for some of the skillful abilities of young basketball players

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Abstract

The aim of the research is to evaluate the training curricula in some of the skillful abilities of the youth basketball players. As for the areas of research, it included the human area, which was represented by Maysan youth basketball players, and the temporal area was determined for the period from (2/16/2023) to (05/15/2023), while the spatial area was in the halls of the clubs researched.

The researcher used the descriptive approach in the manner of repeated measurements, and the research sample consisted of (12) players from the Maysan Youth Basketball Club, and the (SPSS) system was used to obtain the results of the research, and the researcher concluded the following:

- It appeared that there were significant differences in some of the researched skill abilities between the three measurements.
- The training curriculum prepared by the three clubs is good and worked on developing the players skillfully and at different rates.

The researcher recommends the following:

- Using periodic and regular tests as evidence for the players on their level, to be an incentive for them to make a greater effort.
- The researcher recommends the application of tests and standards as an essential part of modern programs for preparation and training.

Keywords: evaluation, training curriculum, skill abilities, youth players, basketball.

تؤيّم من هاج تدريبي لبيض القدرات المهارية للعبى الشباب بكرة السلة م. د مصطفى اسعد
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ال
مستخلص

هدف البحث الى تؤيّم المنهج التدريبي في بعض القدرات المهارية للعبى الشباب بغلس ال باقم اليا الحياقت البحث فبد 1 بتما عابى المحال البشرى الذي نعمل بالعبى باب الى ان بغلس ال اقم ونحدد المحال الزلاني لامس ال ن) 2023/2/16 (لغاية) 2023/05/15 (نبي ن بين كان المحال المةاني في فاعات اقنذبة المبحونة.

واستخدم البانث المنهج الوصفي بأسلوب القياسات المقترسم ونقون عينة البحث ال ن) 12 (ق عبا ال ن زادي ال ان بغلس ال اة الشباب كم نم اسنعمال نظام (SPSS) لاقصول عاى نلوج البحثم واسنننن البانث الاياي:

- ❖ ظمل ان هناك نلوزا الاحوظاى نى بعض القدرات المهارية المبحونة بين القياسات البانث.
- ❖ المنهج التدريبي المعد ال ن قبل اقنذبة البانث جرد وعمل عاى تطويل الال عبين الهارباى وبن ب الخنانة.

ويوصى الباحث بما يلي:

- ❖ استخدام اقنذبات الدورية والمنظمة كدلول لال عبين عاى ال نواهم ليقون ن اقرا لهم لنبل ج همد القبل.
- ❖ يوصى البانث بتطبيق اقنذبات والمقاييس كحزء اساسى لابلالاج الحذبة لال عداد والتدريب.
- ❖ القللمات المنبأحية: تؤيّم الهاج تدريبيم القدرات المهارية للعبى الشباب بغلس ال اة.

مقدمة البحث واهميته: نعد

لعبه بغلس ال اة لاصراقت ال الالعب النلقية المسميزى ال نى يمارسها القنول بين وانشلت انشراا كقبولاً فوزها ناعب نى ال انات صغول سوبأعداد فإياة م نبت ازدادت ن ب الشاهدنها والزاولنها إذ ننتطاب إننازا عباى لاقدرات المهارية النلقية ال ن جمة ون بق العمل ال ع اعضاء الفليق الواند ال ن جهة اخلى.

ويطلب ذلك عملياً تطوير التواصاة لبرنامج التدريبية عن طريق ااختبارات التبعوية لتتعلق المدرب واللاعب على الا وصل اليه ان تطور اذ ان التقييم هو عمارة يتم عن طريق التعلق على درجة او الذي تحقيق الاهداف الموضوعية لعمارة التدريب الرياضي وبهذا فهو عمارة دائمة السمعة طالما ان هناك الحاق للتدريب الخطةم وعى وفق الا تؤدم تأتي اهمية البحث في التعلق على انضال البرنامج التدريبية الثالث وكذلك الذي التطور الحادث بالنسبة لللاعبين ونوايا للاختبارات التبعوية وايضاً التعلق على نقاط التوس والضعف لالاج التدريبية التي يتم عن اقسنتفس لهذا السبب.

2-1 مشكلة البحث: الن

خلال خيلس البانث لوزنه قعباً سبواً وادرب نالهاً ني لعبة كلس الساة قنظ غواب العميات التقييمية بوصفها دليل لاكتشف عن زواط التوس والضعف في الالاج التدريبية لادربين الاعالين في التندية للياضيقم وبثالي تصحح اق الور الخاطئة وتدعيم اق الور اق حابية وكذلك التعلق على انضال البرنامج التدريبية بين اقدنية للياضيقم لتتسنى لادربين اقسنةاعة بتك البرنامج المتوسطة لتطويل عماهمم اذا ارشأى البانث اسخدام ااختبارات الدورية بوصفها دليل للتقييم عمل الدربي اذنية اليهان ونوايا لبعض الودرات المهارية بقلس الساة.

3-1 هدنا البحث:

1- التعلق على التلوق بين الواسات الثالث ونوايا الودرات المهارية لالعبى الشباب كلس الساة.

2- التعلق على نسب التطور ونوايا الودرات المهارية لالعبى الشباب كلس الساة.

4-1 نرض البحث:

1- هناك تلوق ذات دقة انصاثة بين زناج الواسات الثالث (التبعوية) ونوايا لافدرات المهارية ولصالح الواس الثالث .

5-1 مجال البحث:

1-5-1 المجال البشري: قعبو نادي اليهان بقلس الساة.

2-5-1 المجال الزماني : لامس الن 2023/2/16 ولغاثة 2023/5/15.

3-5-1 المجال المكاني: القاعة المغاثة لنادي اليهان اقولمبي .

3- منهجية البحث و اجراءاته الميدانية:

3-1 منهج البحث:

اعتمد البانث اسخدام المنهج الوصفي بأسلوب الواسات المتكلس لوزنه المنهج المل يتم لجل الشفاة البحثم وتحويق اهدفه.

2-3 مجتمع البحث وعينته: تم تحديد

الجمع البحث وهم قعبى الشباب بقلس الساة نبي الحافظة اليهان وهم (نبي اليهان م قاعة صبال م دجابه م اليهان م) وبعبد اقسنتفسار عن نجم المجتمع القاي الن اق اتحاد القلعي لقلس الساة لمحافظة اليهانم تم الحصول على عدد الجمع البحث والبال (48) قعباً م الا عينة البحث تؤد اختار البانث نادي اليهان وهم يتمثلون عينة البحث اللئيسمة والبال عدهم (12) قعباً م وينسبة الويدة (25%) لاموسيم

(اللياضي) 2022-2023.

3-3 الوسائل والجهزة والادوات المستخدمة:

3-3-1 وسائل جمع المعلومات:

• الملاج والمصادر العلنية والجزئية المقابالت الشخصية الع الخلاء وذوي ااختصاص.

3-3-2 الجهزة المستخدمة:

جهاز ناسوب خصي (قبتوب) نوع Compaq 610 (م ناسية القتلونية يدوية عدد 1) (م ساعة تويي القتلونية) 100/1 (الن التانية نوع) Diamond (عدد 2).

3-3-3 الادوات المستخدمة:

• الالعب كلس ساة قانوزيم لي ولس جادي) 50 التل (م لطة قسوة الاوزم و اخص بالسنية عدد 15) (م كلات ساة عدد 10) (م صافلس عدد 2) (م ساعة تويي عدد 2).

4-3 اجراءات البحث الميدانية:

3-4-1 تحديد اختبارات القدرات المهارية المختارة:

قام البانث باعتماد وتحديد ااختبارات المهارية المتوافر في المصادر والملاج وذلك باختيار المجموعة الن ااختبارات المتوسطة :

1- اختبار قوة التهديف الن اللاية للجلس) الازن نسن جاسم م 2007 م 75)

2- اختبار الطبطة العلية) الاق عاي الجمود م 2016 م 262)

3- اختبار المتولة الصدرية) جواد م 2015 م 66)

3-5 الالاج الستطالية:

قام البانث باجراء حلبة اسبطل عية اولية بتطبيق ااختبار تطبيوياً الالاجاً وكان وئاً نينبذ ااختبار يوم النالبناء الموابق (2022/2/18) ني نمم الساة البالبة ظلماً على عينة الن قعبى زادي دجاة اللياضي والبال عدهم (5) قعبينم لمغلفة الويد المسبب لالتنبيذ ااختبارم والصوروات التي تؤد نواجه البانثم والعلقة كناية نلق العمل المساعد نضالاً عن نوسيم الواجات اعابهم والبدى صبالن الالاج ميز والادواتم

والتكبد الن ساللة الالجزس المسعمارة.

ونفيماً يأتي النتائج التي اسفلت عنها التحلية اقسبطل عية الاولى الع التعديالت الواجب العمل بها بما يتالئم الع هذه النتائج:

1. الالامة ااختبار لا عينة تؤد الدراسة.
2. تم تحديد المواقع المناسبة لتطبيق العمل المساعد بما يتالئم الع ااختبار.
3. اقدرات نفي بالغلض الذي وضع الن اجاه.

ثم اجلي التحلية اقس نطال عوة الثانية بتطبيق اق خنبار المهارة عاي عوة العوزة لن) 5 (ق عبين لن زادي) دجاة (عوة النسس العامية) بتاريخ 2023/2/20 وبذلك تم الحصول عاي الوياس اقول إبحاد العالل النباتم وتم اعادس اق خنبار بتاريخ 2023/2/27 عاي العوة زفها لاصول عاي الوياس الثاني لمعالل النبات.
3-6 المعاملات العلمية لاختبارات:

بعد ان تم تطبيق اق خنبارات وُيد الدراسة ني النحارب الـس نطال عوة تم إس نخل اج الـسس العامية لاختبارات والحدول) 1(يبين ذلك
 (الحدول) 1

يبين العالل النبت والصدق الذاتي والموضوعية لاختبارات المهارة

ت	الختبارات المهارة	وندس القياس	معامل النبات	الصدق الذاتي	معامل الموضوعية
1	اختبار دقة التهديف لن اللالية الحلس	درجة	0.864	0.930	0.955
2	اختبار الطبطة العلية	ثانية	0.887	0.942	0.967
3	اختبار المعاوله الصدرية	درجة	0.859	0.927	0.944

3-7 التجربة الرئيسية) الساسية): بعد

ان الكدت نتائج النحارب اقس نطال عوة سالالة العلاءات المنذس وصحنها ونضمزها الشلوط والمواصنات العامية لاختبار نضال عن الالئمها عوة البحت تم تطبيق اق خنبارات المهارة عاي عوة البحت وقوالها) 12 (ق عبا لن ق عبي زادي الوسان بقلس الساة الشباب وذلك في الساعه) الثالثة) ظل ام ونضم من التطبيق ثالث فاسات قبل تطبيق البزلج التدربي المعد لن قبل الدرب الزادي وبعد اللور هل لن التدربات عمد البانث بتطبيق الوياس الثاني) الوسيط(م وبعد اق زنهاه لن ننيذ البزلج وام البانث بتطبيق الوياس الثالث ولمس هل لن لن 2023/3/1 لغاية 2023/5/1 وبواقع ثالث فاسات واختبارات نتجوة .
8-3 الوسائل الحصانية:

اسنعم نيه الحوية الـنصانية الاحازس) SPSS.Ver 21(قس نخل لاج المعاللت اق نصانية:

4- عرض النتائج وتحليلها ومن ائشنتها :-

بعد الازنهاه لن إجلعاءات فواسيات البحت السعوية الثالثة م نيم جم بع البانثات والعالحنها إنصانها م لوعلض البانث نتائجها بالحدول اق نصانية ولن نتم نحاها والنائشها ودعها بالمصادر العامية والدراسات الكاديمية وكالشي :-

1-4 : عرض نتائج اختبارات بعض المتغيرات البدنية والحركية والمهارة السبوية الثالثة للعبدي الزاي قبيل بالكرة الطائرة وتحليلها

ومن ائشنتها :-

1-1-4 : عرض نتائج اختبارات بعض المتغيرات البدنية للواسات السبوية الثالثة للعبدي النابيل بالكرة الطائرة وتحليلها ومن ائشنتها

:-

لوعلض البانث المعالم الـنصانية لافواسات السعوية الثالثة لؤيم نتائج اختبارات بعض الفدرات المهارة المبحوثة م وكما لبين ني الحدول

(2) و (3) و (4) .

جدول (2)

يبين قيم المعالم الـنصانية لافواسات السعوية الثالثة في نتائج اختبارات الفترات المهارة

دقة التحاس	درجة (Sig)	تحاس النبان (Leven)	الواس الثالث		الواس الثاني		القياس الول		وندس القياس	المعغولات الدينية
			ع ±	س	ع ±	س	ع ±	س		
غول دال والتحاس	0.597	0.778	1.165	15.583	0.937	10.167	0.996	7.083	درجة	ختبار دقة التهديف لن اللالية الحلس
غول دال والتحاس	0.564	0.177	0.087	10.046	0.451	11.063	0.839	12.579	ثانية	اختبار الطبطة العلية
غول دال والتحاس	0.286	0.779	0.718	8.167	0.669	6.083	0.779	3.667	درجة	اختبار المعاوله الصدرية

ن = 12 ، غير دال ومتجانس عندم تكون مس توى الدلالة اكبر مل) 0.05 .

نُبين نتائج الحدول) 2(ان فوطني الوس الحسبي والنحلاف المعماري لنتائج عوة البحت ني اختبار فواس) دقة التهديف لن اللالية الحلس(الول باغا (7.083 ± 0.996) م وفي اق اختبار السعوي الثاني اصبح الوس الحسبي والنحلاف المعماري) 10.167 ± 0.937(م وفي اق اختبار السعوي الثالث اصبح الوس الحسبي والنحلاف المعماري) 15.583 ± 1.165(م وباغ فوية تحاس النبان بين الوياسات الثالثة

العنوي ولصالح القياس الثاني	*0.000	3.083	2 - 1	ة التهديف الن اللالفة الحلس
العنوي ولصالح القياس الثالث	*0.000	8.500	3 - 1	
العنوي ولصالح القياس الثالث	*0.000	5.417	3 - 2	
العنوي ولصالح القياس الثاني	*0.000	1.433	2 - 1	اختبار الطبطة العالفة
العنوي ولصالح القياس الثالث	*0.000	2.533	3 - 1	
العنوي ولصالح القياس الثالث	*0.000	1.100	3 - 2	
العنوي ولصالح القياس الثاني	*0.000	2.417	2 - 1	اختبار المناولة الصدرفة
العنوي ولصالح القياس الثالث	*0.000	4.500	3 - 1	
العنوي ولصالح القياس الثالث	*0.000	2.083	3 - 2	

*** الفرق معنوي عن دم تكون مستوى دلالة (≤ 0.05) ، $(n = 12)$ يبين لنا**
 الحدود (4) ان قيمة الفلق في الأوساط الاحبابية بين القياس (اقول والثاني) باغ (3.083 (نج المستوى دلالة) 0.000 (المبايدل عاى وجود فلوغ العنوية بين القياس) اقول والثاني) ولصالح القياس الثاني م وان قيمة الفلوغ في الأوساط الاحبابية بين القياس (اقول والثالث) باغ (8.500) (نج المستوى دلالة) (0.000) (المبايدل عاى وجود فلوغ العنوية بين القياس) اقول والثالث) ولصالح القياس الثالث م بينما باغ قيمة الفلوغ في الأوساط الاحبابية بين القياس (الثاني والثالث) باغ (5.417) (نج المستوى دلالة) (0.000) (المبايدل عاى وجود فلوغ العنوية بين القياس) (الثاني والثالث) ولصالح القياس الثالث .
 نتبين ان ذلك بان هناك تطور الاحوط في المستوى الال عيبن الشيباب في فبالات الشدرطب البن خبال نتبائج القبلوق نبي القياسات الشعيفة الثالثة ني قياس اختبار) دقة التهديف الن اللالفة الحلس).
 وان قيمة الفلق في الأوساط الاحبابية بين القياس (اقول والثاني) باغ (1.433 (نج المستوى دلالة) (0.000) (المبايدل عاى وجود فلوغ العنوية بين القياس) اقول والثاني) ولصالح القياس الثاني م وان قيمة الفلوغ في الأوساط الاحبابية بين القياس (اقول والثالث) باغ (2.533) (نج المستوى دلالة) (0.000) (المبايدل عاى وجود فلوغ العنوية بين القياس) اقول والثالث) ولصالح القياس الثالث م بينما باغ قيمة الفلوغ في الأوساط الاحبابية بين القياس (الثاني والثالث) باغ (1.100) (نج المستوى دلالة) (0.000) (المبايدل عاى وجود فلوغ العنوية بين القياس) (الثاني والثالث) ولصالح القياس الثالث .
 نتبين ان ذلك بان هناك تطور الاحوط في المستوى الال عيبن الشيباب في فبالات الشدرطب البن خبال نتبائج القبلوق نبي القياسات الشعيفة الثالثة ني قياس اختبار) الطبطة العالفة).
 وان قيمة الفلق في الأوساط الاحبابية بين القياس (اقول والثاني) باغ (2.417 (نج المستوى دلالة) (0.000) (المبايدل عاى وجود فلوغ العنوية بين القياس) اقول والثاني) ولصالح القياس الثاني م وان قيمة الفلوغ في الأوساط الاحبابية بين القياس (اقول والثالث) باغ (4.500) (نج المستوى دلالة) (0.000) (المبايدل عاى وجود فلوغ العنوية بين القياس) اقول والثالث) ولصالح القياس الثالث م بينما باغ قيمة الفلوغ في الأوساط الاحبابية بين القياس (الثاني والثالث) باغ (2.083) (نج المستوى دلالة) (0.000) (المبايدل عاى وجود فلوغ العنوية بين القياس) (الثاني والثالث) ولصالح القياس الثالث .
 نتبين ان ذلك بان هناك تطور الاحوط في المستوى الال عيبن الشيباب في فبالات الشدرطب البن خبال نتبائج القبلوق نبي القياسات الشعيفة الثالثة ني قياس اختبار) المناولة الصدرفة).

4-2-1 : مناقشة نتائج اختبارات بعض القدرات المهارية في القياسات التنبؤية الثالثة للعبى الشباب بكرة السلة:- التما نتعدد انواع التؤوم فان لن اهم ادواره هو التشخيص فم إذ ان الدراسة الحالية مي دراسة تقويمية تعتمد التشخيص لتبع الحالة المهارية للعبى الشيباب بقلس الامة الن خلال المقارنة بمستويات التطور الواردس في نتبع الأوساط الاحبابية لقياسات الثالثة بالمقارنة بما كانوا عاوه وكيف اصبحوا بعد تطبيق المزهج التدريبي بملور الدس القياس المحدد والتي نتبئها النتائج لقل الشغول الهاري ني هذه الدراسة م والن خلال النتائج في الجداول المتخلجة لقياسات الثالث نجد ان القياس الثالث هو افضل في جميع القياسات المهارية م ويعد البانث ان سبب هذا التؤوم جاء زنيحة التدریب الموزن والمعد في المزهج التدريبي الن ذبل العادر الفزي بالاضافة الى توفل اقجهزس واقحوات والمالعب المخصصة لتدریب واقسملارفة في التدریب لكون النادي الن اقندبة المتطورس والتي تعتمد عاى قعبيبن ذوي المستويات العالفة كما ان اقسملار ني الوندات التدریبة تحدث تطورا ني الزوانى البدنية والوظيفية وق سبما المهارية لدى الال عيبن الما ننعفس اوحابا عاى اقداء بشقل كبيل.
 وهذا الايؤكد عاوه (المدوح نمدي م 2017 م 47) ان اثنان المهارات لیس كائنا نؤد بقون هناك كبيل الن الال عيبن يتؤون اداء المهارات بشقل جيد ولقن النة الل ني اقداء) وهو الهدف الزهائي (لن عمایة التدریب والذي يزصد به اداء الالعب لمجموع الهارائه اثناء التدریب والمباريات م ويضيف (Reilly and others 2003 م 26) ان نمية صرفت اقداء الحلكي وعراضه لال عيبن نعمل عاى نمية المستوى اقداء المهارى لال عيبن ونطويلهم فاكساب الالعب الصفات الحلكية اقسامة والندبة تساعده ني اداء المهارات المختانة بالصورس المئتم كما نمعهه الن اقسملار دون نعب ني اداء هذه المهارات المختانة بالطلبة النية المطاوية خلال نتلس المبارس.
5- الستجاجات والنوصيات:

1-5 الاستنتاجات:

- 1- ظم ان هناك تطوراً الاحوظاً ني الؤدرات المهارية المبحوئة ونواً لالؤياسات الؤالث.
- 2- المزهج الؤدرية الموعء الن ؤبل الؤادر الؤدرية لؤاى الؤاسان ؤؤم وعمل عاى نطوؤل الال عىبن الهارؤاً وىنهب الؤؤانة.
- 3- ظهل والن ؤال الؤؤؤؤ المؤؤلؤة ان الؤياس الؤالث هو افضؤل لن بىن الؤياسات الؤالث.

2-5 الؤوصيات:

- 1- اسؤؤام اقؤؤبارات الؤورية والمؤؤؤمة لؤؤل لال عىبن عاى الؤؤاهم لؤؤون ن افزا لهم لىل ؤمء الؤؤل.
- 2- يؤوصى الؤانؤ بؤطبىق اقؤؤبارات والمؤافىس ؤؤء اساسى لابلالؤ الؤؤؤة لال عؤاء والؤؤؤب.
- 3- اعؤماء الؤننالؤ الؤدرية الموعء الن ؤبل الؤادر الؤدرية لؤاى الؤاسان بؤؤل الؤؤاب الؤ ؤبل اقؤؤة اقؤؤى .
- 4- ضؤورس اؤلاء ءراسة الشابه عاى نؤؤت عملؤة اؤلى والؤؤؤل ات اؤلى.

المصاؤر العربىة والؤؤبىة:

- ❖ الاق عاى الؤموء: نأؤل اسؤؤام نؤلؤنؤاؤ ؤاؤة بالؤؤوات المؤاعس فى نعام الهارس الؤبؤة بؤؤل الؤؤم الؤؤة الؤبؤة الؤبؤة الؤبؤة الؤؤة بؤؤام الؤالؤ والؤؤؤلونم العء الؤالؤم 2016.
- ❖ رعد عىء الؤؤؤم ؤواؤ: نأؤل وساؤل نعاؤؤة الؤؤاة فى نؤالؤ اقؤؤة الؤؤبؤة وؤؤبىن بعض المهارات اقؤؤة بؤؤل الؤؤة م رسالؤ الاؤؤؤل ؤؤل الؤؤورس م ؤالؤة بؤؤام م 2015.
- ❖ الازن نؤن ؤاسم: اؤل اسؤؤام وسىاة الؤاعس فى نطوؤل ءؤة الؤؤؤى فى الؤالؤة الؤس بؤؤل الؤؤم الؤؤة عاوم الؤبؤة الؤبؤة الؤؤم الؤؤاقولم العء الؤاعم 2008.
- ❖ المءوؤ الؤمءى: سؤؤؤلؤؤة الؤوز وؤؤؤى الال عىبن فى لؤس الؤؤم ط1م القاهلسم للؤؤ الؤؤاب لانؤلم 2017.
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British Journal of sports medicine London. 2003.

English Teaching in Agricultural Universities

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Abstract: This study looked into the quality of English instruction in agricultural universities in Uzbekistan. English is a supplemental subject offered in agricultural universities to equip students for global communication issues. Following graduation and post-graduation, students prepare to serve in a variety of local and worldwide organizations and corporations. Because English is the primary medium of communication in the business, English demands additional emphasis in addition to students' subjective skills. Employers frequently advise candidates to improve their English language skills when recruiting. As a result, teaching and mastering English is an important priority for agricultural universities. The researcher focused on many stages of students' academic connection with English in this study, including students' academic competency in English upon admission, needs analysis, syllabus design, course aims as ESP, content quality, hours invested, and assessment.

Key words: Syllabus design, ESP, EAP, CLTA, needs assessment

Introduction

English is presently regarded as the world's most prominent lingua franca. It is an integral aspect of the academic and professional sectors. From an academic standpoint, English is taught to participants in order to equip them to face global language issues. It addresses both the curriculum and the syllabus. Employers frequently need higher levels of English competence in the professional sphere. Organizations, particularly multinational corporations, recruit their human resources from multilingual populations. This technique benefits organizations based on their level of technological ability. Employees from various linguistic origins require a common language to digest ideas and actions. This job has been held by English. Effective staff communication and company connection with external entities demand exceptional English performance. Thus, the degree of the participant's academic relationship with English effects their recruitment and standing in the relevant companies. Because Uzbekistan is an agriculturally focused country, there are hundreds of enterprises and organizations seeking to grow the industry. These businesses and organizations typically hire graduates of agricultural institutions. Recruiters frequently detect English language weaknesses during assessments. A number of candidates have just rudimentary English abilities despite their professional expertise. As a result, human resource specialists frequently recommend that potential employees improve their English language skills. To justify the scenario, the university syllabus design comes first as a worry. As a result, the study topic is to identify appropriate techniques for developing second language learning in agricultural university courses. This investigation focuses heavily on the agricultural education system, because when HR teams recruit a group of employees to serve at the national and international levels, their English proficiency reduces overall company performance, including negotiations, project adoptions, and scholarships for higher education. Inappropriate hiring results in a loss of money and employee quality. The purpose of this research was to better understand the curriculum and syllabus design of academic English at four agricultural institutions. The way needs analyses are maintained in these curricula, as well as the degree of implementation in the classroom, are also taken into account. Needs assessment considers both academic and professional views. Observation and survey methods were used to acquire data about syllabuses. Finally, this study suggests some potential ideas that may be developed in those universities.

Methodology: In order to perform the aforementioned inquiry, the researcher must first establish a theoretical foundation by reading certain literature. These concerns are addressed in pedagogical research.

Curriculum: According to Candlin (1984) and Nunan (1988), curriculum is the broad presentation of "language learning, learning purpose and experience, evaluation, and the role of teacher-learner relationships." Nunan (1988) divides curriculum into two categories: planning and implication.

A syllabus provides a limited picture of language acquisition. According to Candlin (1984), a syllabus is a specialized presentation of linguistic resources that are "more localized and are based on accounts and records of what actually happens at the classroom level as teachers and learners apply a given curriculum to

their own situation." The contents of the syllabus are assessed based on implicational variables derived from the curriculum. Nunan (1988) divides curriculum into two groups. The first is a product-oriented curriculum, which focuses on "the knowledge and skills that learners should gain." It has one significant category: functional-notional syllabus. Another is process oriented syllabus, also known as procedural syllabus, which delivers material that is "organized around tasks, rather than in terms of grammar or vocabulary" (Richards, Platt, and Weber, 1985 in Nunan, 1988). The implementation of "techniques and procedures for collecting information to be used in syllabus design" (Nunan, 1988) is referred to as needs analysis. It is divided into two streams. The first is learner analysis, which makes use of participant data. Through a survey, it covers specific issues concerning learners, such as gender or race, as well as professional position. The second step is task analysis, which refers to the selection of activities that may be assigned to participants as a classroom or practical exercise while focusing on the concerns identified during learner analysis. The combination of these two elements is critical in evaluating the data offered in this paper. In agricultural institutes, the Communicative Language Teaching Approach (CLTA): The Communicative Language Teaching Approach (CLTA) is now the most well-known English Language Teaching (ELT) curriculum. It focuses on four types of communication skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. It produces language phrases by following generic and minimal, but not zero, grammatical functions. CLTA's objective, according to Richards and Rodgers (1986), is "learning to communicate." The CLTA syllabus necessitates a combination of concept and function. Experts recommend different syllabus modules at various times. Yalden (1983) illustrated some of the most important communicative syllabus kinds. Because English is the medium of teaching at universities, English as a supplemental subject should be given. Their requirements are divided into two categories: academic and professional.

In order to finish their academic activity, former pupils must understand English. General study, class lecture, class quizzes, examinations, presentations, drafting thesis or research paper, academic article for journal, and other activities may be included. They need basic and intermediate English grammar as well as a large vocabulary to accomplish their tasks. Linguistic performance enhances their academic knowledge presentation in examinations. As a result, the emphasis here is solely on language rather than task-based activities. The latter, professional dimension, refers to how to equip pupils to face the rigors of a competitive professional life. Application, cover letter, CV, business English (memos), official dealings (joining letter, letter of reference, letter of recommendation, letter of acceptance, letter of rejection, letter of resignation), competitive writing (translation, instant paragraph/essay on contemporary writings, free-hand writing, etc.), and documentation are all examples of writing genres. In terms of "speaking" ability, it includes effective communication using influential languages as well as excellent word choices (managing situation and negotiation), social English as well as identifying formal and informal situations (greeting, introducing, welcoming, thanking, saying bye, farewell, asking advice/suggestion, giving advice, offering something, inviting, asking for opinion, agreeing, disagreeing, complaining, apologizing, responding to apology, and so on), interview (preparation, language code, possible interview questions and answers), Professional presentation (plans, preparation, and evaluation areas), coping with difficult and competitive teams, public speaking, and so on. Professionals must determine the proper sound code as well as the necessary IPA for "listening" purposes. Every instruction and query should be clearly and firmly understood. These are the potential requirements for English as a supplemental course. Basic grammatical things are highlighted in these curricula, while advanced topics are left out. Professional abilities are included, but only briefly. Students must learn social and business English since these abilities will pave the route for them to reach the pinnacle of professional achievement. If these talents are not thoroughly explored alongside students' subjective domains, their work performance decreases. The questionnaire addresses instruction, internal learning (academic), external learning (professional), and personal impressions of participants. Some challenges in data display have evolved in three categories: positive, negative, and suggestion. Positively, a huge number of students have taken English as a course. A number of respondents are able to speak well with international teams who often visit this country for various commercial and corporate activities, but many participants, although possessing professional abilities, have no clear understanding of social and business English. Despite the fact that many of them are prepared for professional or work areas, they lack self-confidence in their English skills. They understand that English, along with subjective expertise such as official responsibilities assigned to them in various agricultural sectors in agriculture-based organizations or agencies, is also

associated with their professional success, but they often fall short of developing the necessary competence. As a result, they advise the individual colleges to place a greater emphasis on this communicative talent, which is required in all aspects of life, both academic and professional. The researcher draws some conclusions and recommendations based on the aforesaid analysis. To begin with, syllabus design is a critical topic. The majority of the programs at these colleges are theoretical in nature. Some of which, in terms of curriculum design, are not well adapted to current labor market need. It is true that students in agricultural institutions are not required to be language experts, which is a cause for concern, and this should be more of a reason for students to practice and perfect competency in General English. Based on this study, a proposal is made: colleges should divide the dimensions into two categories. The first stream is academic, with information designed to help students achieve in academic exams using English as the medium of communication. The second point to make is about professional communication. Students should prepare themselves for exceptional professional performance in this course, where they may grasp management tactics for professional skills. That is, the role of English is critical in both cases.

Conclusion

Excellent English proficiency is the ultimate key to academic and professional success. The preceding discussion covered data analysis through theoretical difficulties. Participants shared their thoughts and early comments on syllabus design and the value of English in the workplace. The analysis, debates, and suggestions mirror the reality that agricultural institutions are developing their present English teaching system. The development of English with technical skill is required to attain a leading position in the employment market. Because agricultural colleges in Uzbekistan are making significant contributions in their different fields, they should share their success and benefit with the rest of the globe. To get this area, an English language course must meet worldwide standards, which include an improved and advanced curriculum design, a standard learning technique, and enjoyable class time. Students may be provided special classes to help them improve their communication abilities. Because the agriculture industry is now a member of the global village. The agriculture sector's branding is in high demand. As a result, Agriculture and English should be conducted together.

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The role of technology in improving reading skills

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Abstract: The information I have provided below is a general technique that can be used in the process of teaching children of school age to read. This is a useful way to help my students improve their reading skills

Key Words: technology, improving, reading, skills, introduction, systems, reading, comprehension, education, prerequisite, participation, availability, technologies, web-based, resources, communications, educational.

Reading is an important speech skill and one of the means of communication, a skill which enables people to get written messages. Reading is a part of daily life for people who live in literate communities. Urban technological societies, as C. Wallace states, operate on the premise that their members can read. So, reading is a very important skill, both the aim and the means of teaching.

Now to generalize, people usually seek information for some purpose (to find out what is happening or happened; to know when or where something will happen or what will be available, etc.) or because they are interested in some topic. they study for.

Whatever the reasons for reading may be, we read because we want to get something from the writing, this something can be called the message, it might be facts, ideas, feelings, enjoyment, etc. Summarising up different reasons mentioned, four general ideas. Since the introduction of writing systems, reading comprehension has always been fundamental to success in several areas of education and other systems, and is a prerequisite for successful participation in most areas of adult and youth life. The proliferation of mass media and television, radio, magazines, newspapers, and other technologies and web resources has enabled the development of distance learning activities, case management, and other distance communication in both educational and clinical settings. I use modern techniques along with different technical methods in developing students' reading skills and it can help. Currently, there are some studies in the available literature and sample techniques such as telephone, laptop, electronic book, electronic dictionary, audio book, and other types that have studied the effectiveness of Internet-based programs for children with reading comprehension difficulties. but almost no one has considered remote applications. In this article, I will provide information and express my opinion about the remote classroom program developed at the school to improve language and reading comprehension (the program is a convenient and understandable guide and story for students of a particular school). One of the program was held by the scientists that 28 children with difficulty in understanding from 3rd to 6th grade were involved. These children completed the remote program for 15-20 minutes at least three times a week for approximately 4 months. The program was presented to each child individually, at a level of difficulty adapted to his characteristics. Reading comprehension (distinguishing between graded narrative and informational texts) increased after the intervention. These findings are intellectually and educationally important because they suggest that reading comprehension can be developed using a remote individualized program, avoiding the need to transfer children to a rehabilitation center. These children completed the remote program for 15-20 minutes at least three times a week for approximately 4 months. The program was presented to each child individually, at a level of difficulty adapted to his characteristics. Reading comprehension (distinguishing between graded narrative and informational texts) increased after the intervention. These findings have clinical and educational implications because they suggest that reading comprehension can be improved with a remote individualized program, avoiding the need to transfer children to a rehabilitation center. These children completed the remote program for 15-20 minutes at least three times a week for approximately 4 months. The program was presented to each child individually, at a level of difficulty adapted to his characteristics. That is, after completing the book after the specified time, he will go to the next level. Reading comprehension (the ability to distinguish between the ability to simultaneously comprehend the assessed narrative and informational texts and to understand the content of the text or book being read) increased after the intervention. These findings have clinical and educational implications because they

show that reading comprehension can be developed with a distance individual program based on the changes children need to understand the problems in the books and stories they read. Reading comprehension (distinguishing between graded narrative and informational texts) increased after the intervention. These findings have clinical and educational implications because they suggest that reading comprehension can be improved with a remote individualized program, avoiding the need to transfer children to a rehabilitation center. Reading comprehension (distinguishing between graded narrative and informational texts) increased after the intervention. These studies have clinical and educational value because they encourage children to understand the nature of problems and to solve problems, which in turn motivates children to solve problems.

I found the top 10 strategies for teaching reading to be good in my research and used these 10 techniques throughout my research:

I first assessed the student's ability,

I studied with a student,

I used visual guides,

I assigned study buddies by age and class

I made audiobooks

I taught academic English

I asked the students to summarize what they had read

I introduced the students to different forms of speech and after meeting the above requirements step by step, the problems related to reading in young students began to be solved. All the procedures and requirements listed above change depending on the class and age, that is, if it is easy for the younger classes, it will be difficult for the older classes.

Before teaching reading effectively, I must emphasize that understanding the key components of reading instruction is essential. If we do not follow this guide or manual completely, we will face difficulties in the research process. Divided into five main elements, the study guide is very accessible and easy to understand. The five elements of teaching reading.

Phonics: The relationship between letters and the different sounds they make. Using an audio dictionary is helpful. It can be connected using letters or letters. This made it easier for my students to pronounce sounds with letters and words.

For phonemic input: see where consonants or vowels go to make words and send them through. Examples of phonemic awareness include identifying rhyming words, identifying alliteration, dividing a sentence into words, managing syllables in a word, and mixing and matching onsets and pronouns. More precisely, it is convenient to learn this technique at home.

Vocabulary: the range that the learner understands and can use in context. Using the required words will help you better. Using an audio dictionary is useful.

Fluency: reading and picking up words with accuracy, speed and speed. it is useful to use an audio dictionary.

Comprehension: shows the complete information given by the text. After he finished reading, I reanalyzed him, which helped him reconstruct the content of the text he had read and helped the reader to remember it.

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The importance of idioms in speech

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Abstract: In this article you will gain main information about idioms and using them correctly. In addition, you may find the number of replies for questions like what are idioms, what are the types of idioms, how are idioms structured and why are idioms used? You will be given information to increase IELTS score by using idioms, give tips for using them in exact place and examples of idioms. Finally, given interesting exercise in order to understand the meaning and learn utilizing them correctly.

Key words: idioms, peculiar phraseology, pure idioms, binomial idioms, partial idioms and prepositional idioms.

What is an idiom?

An idiom is a type of phrase or expression that has meaning that cannot be deciphered by defining the individual words. The idioms contain more than two or three words, however the meaning of them equal one word. Approximately, the word “idiom” is derived from the ancient Greek word “idioma”, which means “peculiar phraseology”. Maybe, you have troubles to realize the meaning of idioms, therefore you do not pay attention for only one word. To understand idioms is to see the forest for trees, or to look at phrase as a whole rather than focusing on the individual words, example: pull yourself together = calm down.

What are the types of idioms?

Frankly speaking, in our speech there are four types of idiom such as pure idioms, binomial idioms, partial idioms and prepositional idioms.

1. Pure idioms: this is your typical idiom, the meaning of which cannot be deduced by its individual components. When someone says, “Spill the beans”, they are asking someone to reveal a secret, not pour out a can of beans. But you would not know that by looking at each word of that phrase.
2. Binomial idiom: this idiom is a phrase that contains two words joined by a conjunction or a preposition. Some examples include “by and large” (everything considered), “dos and don'ts” (guidelines on what to do and/or avoid in a certain situation), and “heart-to-heart” (a candid conversation between two people).
3. Partial idiom: this idiom is one that's been shortened into one part, with the second part generally being understood by fluent speakers. People often use the partial idiom “when in Rome”, with understanding that the other person knows the second part: “do as the Romans do”.
4. Prepositional idiom: this idiom is a phrase that combines a verb and a preposition to create a verb with a distinct meaning. The phrase “agree on” is a prepositional idiom that combines the verb “agree” with the preposition “on” and is used to express that you share an opinion with someone.

How are idioms structured?

The structures of idioms are essentially their syntactic behaviour. This behaviour cannot be predicted solely on the basis of their form or figurative meaning alone, but it must be due to some relation between the form and meaning. An idiom is an institutionalized and conventionalized sequence of at least two words or free morphemes that is semantically restricted so that it functions as a single lexical unit, whose meaning cannot or can only to a certain extent be deduced from the meaning of its constituents. Idioms are characterized as having conventional meaning, figuration, inflexibility of form, and provability. Idioms have been called ‘multiword units’, metaphors, phrasemes, fixed expressions and formulaic expressions. Structurally, idioms do not form a unique class of linguistic items such that all idioms belong to it, but that they share many of the same properties normally associated with more literal expressions.

Why are idioms used? Idioms are really fundamental for our speech. When we use idioms for our speech or sometimes writing, this helps in order to add to variety and color, as well as they can be used to emphasize a point, or to make a statement more memorable. In addition, idioms are based on historical events and mostly common human trials (experiences)

REMINDER

If you use idioms in IELTS speaking exam, this helps to increase your level.

Using idioms during speaking of IELTS, it becomes more beautiful your speech. Since most native speakers utilize idioms in their everyday conversation without much thought. Most importantly, using idioms correctly is really essential in your speech. Here are a few tips on how to do so:

1. Make sure you understand the meaning of the idioms before using it
2. Pay attention to the context in which the idiom is being used.
3. Be careful not to overuse idioms.

Exercises:

Match the give idioms with definition.

1. To be tickled pink	a. To fell little sick/ill
2. It is not my cup of tea	b. I could not sleep well
3. To love someone to bits	c. To be very sad
4. To be fed up to the back teeth	d. To think carefully before making decisions
5. To be down in the dumps	e. To love someone a lot
6. To feel under the weather	f. To be very happy
7. To sleep on it	g. To be really fed up
8. I could not sleep a wink	h. I do not like it

The best 10 examples of idioms

1. To be tickled pink – to be very happy
2. It is not my cup of tea – I do not like it
3. To love someone to bits – to love someone a lot
4. To be fed up to the back teeth – to be really fed up
5. To be down in the dumps – to be very sad
6. To feel under the weather – to feel a little sick/ill
7. To sleep on it – to think carefully before making a decision
8. I could not sleep a wink – I could not sleep well
9. It drives me round the bend – it makes me crazy
10. It blew me away – it impressed me

Try to use them during your communication because of beauty in your speech. I give information about research which carried out between students about using idioms. Given some questions for students like do you use idioms in your daily speech? and what do you think using idioms good or not? 20 students gave response for these above ones and most of them said ‘I do not utilize idiom my daily communication since catching the meaning may be a bit difficult for others’, for next question they said ‘using idiom is fundamental and useful for our speech but we need to utilize with limit because if we use lot of idioms during interaction, this can change the meaning of our sentences’. As for me, using idioms correctly in my daily speech is a bit challenging but sometimes I use them in order to be more beautiful my speech, additionally we could express our feeling and emotions by helping with idioms. In my opinion, idioms decorate our speech and sentences like ornaments, as well as this helps to increase our mark during exam. To conclude, learning idioms with examples and their meaning is the best way to master them and make your speaking more engaging. Only when they are utilized correctly and in the appropriate contexts can idioms be an effective language tool.

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Special directions of tourism development in Bukhara region: problems and solutions.

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Abstract: This article contains information about tourism, forms of tourism, activities aimed at the development of tourism in Bukhara region, problems and solutions related to the improvement of tourism.

Keywords: Tourism, marketing research, market research, respondent, advertising and sales channels, Bukhara tourism.

Uzbekistan attracts the attention of the whole world with its many historical and architectural monuments, diverse climate and rapid development.

Over the centuries, Uzbekistan was located on the path of trade, merchants and travelers, geographers and missionaries, invaders and conquerors of the Great Silk Road. At the same time, Uzbekistan is becoming one of the fascinating tourist destinations for those interested in the enterprising, culture, history, tradition and exotic countries.¹

Bukhara has been a densely populated center of the oasis since ancient times. He is 2500 years old. Bukhara, which has preserved more than 140 ancient architectural monuments and a comfortable atmosphere, remains one of the favorite places of tourists.

The mausoleum of Ismail Samoni covered with a net, the huge fortress and the strong residence of the ruler of Bukhara, the Ark, Minarai Kalon, many mosques and madrasahs like a living labyrinth, caravansary palaces, and monuments such as baths are among the incomparable jewels of holy Bukhara remains.²

Based on the above considerations, we implemented marketing research aimed at "Development of tourism in Bukhara".

Many people understand Marketing Research and Market Research as the same activity. It is known that "market research" includes the quantitative assessment and analysis of the market itself, while marketing research covers all factors affecting the marketing of goods and services. That is, it includes the study of the effectiveness of advertising and sales channels, the analysis of marketing methods of products and competing firms, as well as all issues related to consumer behavior.³

After selecting the persons to be surveyed, the researcher contacts them using the following methods: personal interview, mail questionnaire, and telephone interview. Let's start our review of these methods with a phone conversation. The main disadvantage of this method is that the owners of personal phones form a certain group of the population. True, earlier they paid more attention to this factor. Nowadays, a conversation on the phone is becoming more important in conducting a quick and active survey. Telephone conversation is convenient for researching the markets of industrial goods. It should be short and to the point to be effective. Otherwise, the interview may distract the interviewer and end prematurely. The advantage of conducting a survey by mail is that it is possible to establish communication with any family and entrepreneur with very little effort. In this case, it is also prohibited to replace the results of the survey with the fault of the interview. However, the main disadvantage of this method is the low response rate for mailed requests. A 50% response rate is considered a very good result.⁴

¹ <http://www.uzbekistan-geneva.ch/turizm-191.html>

² <http://www.uzbekistan-geneva.ch/turizm-191.html>

³ <https://www.elib.buxdu.uz/index.php/pages/referatlar-mustaqil-ish-kurs-ishi/item/13610-marketing-tadqiqotlari-va-uning-bosqichlari>

⁴ <https://www.elib.buxdu.uz/index.php/pages/referatlar-mustaqil-ish-kurs-ishi/item/13610-marketing-tadqiqotlari-va-uning-bosqichlari>

This questionnaire is aimed at "Development of tourism in Bukhara", in which we asked the residents of Uzbekistan to express their opinions about Bukhara tourism. All age groups were included in the questionnaire, and more than half of the respondents (57,5%) were people between 21-30 years old. 20% were occupied by people under 20 years old, 7,5-12,5% by 31-40 and 41-50-year-olds.

57,5% of survey participants are women and 42,5% are men. As for their activities, most of the respondents answered that they are students, which is 65% of the number of participants. In addition, 8 people work in budget organizations and 4 people in private enterprises. The share of retired and unemployed respondents equals 5%.

As for the places of residence of the respondents, 87,5% of participants live in Bukhara, 7,5% live in Tashkent, and 5% live in Samarkand.

The questionnaire mainly contains questions about tourist and dining places in Bukhara, and the first question is: how often do you visit tourist places in Bukhara region? - was. 29,3% of people answered this question once a month, and 22% answered once a quarter. The number of visitors once a year was 19,5%, the indicator of this stratum is 5% more than the number of visitors several times a week. The number of non-visitors is only 9,8%.

It was found out that people mainly aim to visit new places when planning their trip, 61% of such respondents made up 56,1% of the population who prioritized closeness to nature. The price/quality and novelty study goals are in the next places, with 36,6 and 31,7 percent.

Among the respondents, it was felt that there is interest in many tourism activities, such as pilgrimage tourism, gastronomic tourism, and visiting event fairs were the most chosen destinations, which received about 45% of the total respondents' votes. Cultural-educational and ethnographic tourism ranks next in popularity. These indicators make up 31,7% and 36,6% of the total respondents. Wellness was 29,3% and Oasis tourism was 14,6%. Tourist indicators for sports and commercial purposes equaled 9,8%.

85% of the respondents prefer to plan their holidays independently, while 15% turn to tourist agents. 53,7% of respondents chose the most optimal option for vacationing in the spring season. 39% of respondents consider summer to be the best time to relax. 7,3% of votes corresponded to winter and autumn seasons.

The service level of tourist places in Bukhara region is set as 7 on average (24,5%), but indicators that collected more responses indicate good service quality.

The next request in the questionnaire is to evaluate the activity of food centers in different categories:

The price is 30 people

Online ordering - 23 people

Quality/taste - satisfying and excellent balance 18 people

Restaurants - 22 people

Service - 27 people

Is defined as satisfactory by the most interesting thing here is that the bad category of online ordering is significantly higher than the others.

53,7% chose hotels as the most preferred choice for overnight stay during the trip, 19,5% chose to spend the night in nature, and 7,3% chose home hotels. 14,6% of the population said that they are not interested in this question.

The following are the main factors hindering the development of tourism in Bukhara.

92,7% of respondents expressed their desire to visit Bukhara again, only 7,3% of participants indicated that they did not have such a desire.

From this survey, it can be analyzed that the main flow of tourists is in the spring and summer seasons, therefore, it is necessary to adapt the activities of tourist attractions to these seasons, and to focus on the organization of tourist attractions or events that can attract tourists in winter and autumn need.

I think this is due to the fact that there are not many favorable rates or the population is not aware of these rates. If tour agents engage in more advertising and offer affordable rates to the population, the flow of tourists will increase.

But for those who like to plan their own trips, it is necessary to pay attention to the improvement of facilities in the infrastructure.

Most of the respondents said that proximity to nature and visiting new places are more important to them than price. Based on this, the organization of more touristic places close to nature and places for recreation will help to create more tourist factor.

Bukhara's tourism sector can be further improved by solving such problems and by increasing marketing channels to inform about these places.

To realize the long-term vision, it is necessary to develop a strategic framework that builds on the main strengths of tourism in the Bukhara region, addresses its main weaknesses, reflects the main opportunities and is resilient to the main threats. Analysis of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) is presented in Table 1:

Table –1
Analysis of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT)

Strengths	Weaknesses
Pristine natural resources, unique tangible and intangible cultural heritage, and diversity across Bukhara region. ▪ Low population density even in metropolitan cities, making it a safe tourist destination.	▪ High cost and poor air connectivity between CAREC capitals and distant markets. ▪ Inadequate transportation infrastructure, roadside facilities on tourist routes, last mile

<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Diversity and uniqueness of nomadic and sedentary cultures throughout the region, ethnic groups and religions.▪ Historic cities, heritage of ancient empires and UNESCO World Heritage Sites in the country.▪ Quality of accommodation and other tourist facilities in the capital and cities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ access, tourist services and signage at tourist sites.▪ Cumbersome and time-consuming border crossing and visa procedures (including at airports).▪ Lack of brand awareness and image, resulting in a lack of knowledge of Uzbekistan and a poor perception of them as tourism destinations.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Growing international interest and recognition of the Silk Road.▪ Continuous expansion of international tourism, especially to fast growing Asian markets, and travelers seeking new experiences and unusual destinations.▪ Major regional infrastructure projects being developed in the region.▪ The continued growth of information technology to enable potential travelers to collect information and interact digitally with potential service providers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Growing global health risks and geopolitical conflicts with serious potential implications for the travel and tourism industry.▪ Climate change with global warming and environmental degradation.▪ Security and political instability in some border countries with Uzbekistan.

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International accounting models and their characteristics in the conditions of innovative economy.

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Abstract: This article presents a number of analytical data on the management of accounting in international markets, models, their description, characteristics, content and essence of international models.

Key words: Management system, economic and social relations, Accounting, financial reporting, international standards, Anglo-American model, Continental model, South American model, International model, Islamic model.

In modern conditions, the success of business entities increasingly depends on their awareness and ability to effectively use information about their internal resources and external market environment.

A new type of society is being formed in which knowledge plays a decisive role in the world system, and it is characterized by:

The development of rational decisions at different levels of the management system requires the processing of a large amount of data, complex procedures of their comparison, analysis and interpretation.

Thus, fundamental changes are taking place in the field of receiving, exchanging and processing information. The expansion of opportunities for global informatization of the economic space is dialectically interconnected with the need for appropriate changes in the theory and practice of accounting, which is the most important element of information and analytical supply for managing the economic activity of the organization.

At the end of the 20th - beginning of the 21st century, qualitative changes are taking place both in the accounting theory of the 21st century and in the practical direction of the accounting science due to the increase in the development dynamics of economic and social relations.

Accounting reports become the basis for the preparation, adoption and implementation of decisions by various user groups. In order to increase its reliability and transparency, the world professional community is actively working on the development of a single conceptual framework for the introduction of international financial reporting standards (IFRS).

As part of the strategic approach that emerged in accounting, analysis, planning, financial reporting includes not only indicators describing the financial position and financial results, but also non-financial information, for example, about non-financial risks. must also be entered.

It is required to develop methods of evaluation for new accounting objects, such as intellectual capital, customer base, methods of calculating the cost of innovative products.

The accounting system faces the problems of combining various types of accounting: management, tax, social, environmental and others.

Modeling for economic activity, which is a complex process with a high level of uncertainty, including many subjects, various resources and means of production, has great cognitive value as a research method.

Accounting in the modern world is the formation of systematic information about objects and preparation of accounting (financial) reports based on it. Such information is essential for all interested parties. But the principles of preparing financial statements are not always consistent, because these principles are influenced by economic, social, cultural, political factors, which together form the accounting system and national reporting principles in a particular country. At the same time, it should be understood that economic, political, social and other changes in one country can directly or indirectly affect the economy of another country, which in turn affects the accounting system. The result of this influence is the creation of a single accounting system for countries with similar principles.

Accounting information is generated based on the requirements of interested users. The needs of users in different countries are different. As a result of solving tasks set by users, an accounting system is formed, the complexity of which directly depends on the level of development of the country's economy.

Most accounting professionals believe that no two countries in the world have the same accounting system. Although all countries of the world use an accounting method in which data is reflected in at least two accounting records, they form an accounting record, but they explain and apply this method in different ways. However, despite this, countries with similar accounting principles are combined into certain accounting models.

There are the following basic models of accounting:

Let's look at the features of each of these models.

The main models of international accounting	Countries using the model	Unique features
Anglo-American	Great Britain, the USA and the Netherlands	The main goal of this model is to ensure the interests of investors and creditors with minimal government intervention in the accounting data creation system.
Continental	Austria, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Italy, France, Switzerland, etc.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A distinctive feature of the continental accounting model is the high level of government intervention in the accounting system in organizations. 2. In such countries, all accounting is regulated by the state: 3. Unlike the Anglo-American model, where the stock market has a great influence on the accounting system, the continental model is characterized by a strong influence of tax legislation.
South America	Countries like Argentina, Brazil, Uruguay, Paraguay, Ecuador	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The South American accounting model is characterized by the fact that the reporting indicators are corrected taking into account the general level of prices, because inflationary processes affected the formation of accounting. 2. For the most reliable reflection of the report indicators, an adjustment is made for inflation. Such correction of the report is aimed at the interests of the state, which needs to fulfill the revenue part of the budget. 3. Also, the focus on public reporting in the South American model is related to the use of information from financial statements to guide fiscal policy. 4. This model uses an international chart of accounts, as a result of which reporting is transparent and accounting data can be compared with international standards.
International	Transnational corporations, global companies and their branches	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Customized financial accounting table; the use of several accounting tables for reporting according to management needs or national standards of branches in other countries. 2. Using flexible rules for creating announcements with the help of financial accounting groups for calculations, nomenclature, cash, income and expenses (HFC). 3. Apply placement templates. 4. Using a report generator to prepare financial reporting forms, including a set of predefined reporting forms with a hierarchical structure of indicators. 5. Organization of accounting based on the methodological model of presentation of posting and report templates.
Islamic	All Islamic countries	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Accurate calculation of Zakat (annual mandatory tax in favor of needs). fair distribution of received income.

		2. Creation and development of activities permitted by Islam, with the guarantee that the activities of Islamic companies will contribute to the socio-economic development of society. 3. It is necessary to observe the prohibition of speculation (interest on loans) (riba) income, the exclusion of elements of uncertainty (gharar) and excitement (maysir) from the company's activities. 4. The main unique tools of Islamic accounting: Zakat, Mubara, Mudoraba, Sukuk, Istisno', Ijara, Salam and others.
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In the continental model, the main users of financial statements are the government and banks. Such a high role of the state is connected with the historical aspect - the centuries-old tradition of centralization of management and the desire of entrepreneurs to receive state support. It follows that the accounting system in the continental model is primarily aimed at meeting the needs of the state. The continental model also includes the principles of accounting profit adjustment to determine tax liabilities.

Main characteristics of accounting models

Accounting model	The main characteristic
Anglo-American	Focusing on the interests of investors, creditors and shareholders.
Continental	High level of state intervention in the accounting policy of organizations
South America	Carrying out the fiscal policy of state bodies
International	International orientation to the interests of multinational corporations and foreign participants in the international currency market.
Islamic	The factor of Islamic religion prevails, implies the prohibition of speculative income and a number of activities.

Studying accounting in different countries makes it possible to analyze what problems exist in the formation and development of accounting in certain countries, what tasks are given the highest priority, what accounting is based on and built on. Accounting as a discipline is enriched by such research. In conclusion, it should be noted that due to the fact that accounting today strives to unify standards, many countries are trying to approximate the rules of accounting in organizations, thereby bringing accounting principles to uniform standards.

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TOURISM AUTHORITY OF UZBEKISTAN: CURRENT ACHIEVEMENTS AND PROBLEMS AS AN EXAMPLE OF TOURISM AND TOURIST CENTERS OF KASHKADARYA

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Abstract: This article provides detailed information about the tourism potential of Kashkadarya region: achievements and problems in the field. In addition, detailed comments on the reforms implemented in the field and their results are presented.

Key words: tourist, tourist, visit, guide, tour operator, tour itinerary, tourism industry, pilgrimage tourism

Uzbekistan is rightfully recognized as one of the destinations of spiritual recreation, i.e. pilgrimage tourism, in the entire Islamic world. There are many reasons for this. In particular, there are many monuments and historical places related to the development of various denominations in our country.

Necessary measures are being implemented in our country for rapid economic, organizational and legal development of the tourism sector, more effective use of the tourism potential of the regions, and fundamental improvement of the management of the tourism network. The land of Kashkadarya occupies an important place in the development of the field with its rich history, ancient artifacts, monuments of the past, unique nature. Today, 1,311 objects of cultural heritage are registered in Kashkadarya region, of which 1,41 are archeology, 200 are architecture, 43 are statues, and 27 are attractions. Along with the protection of these cultural heritage objects, it is very important to carry out reconstruction and repair work in them. There are many examples of our national heritage, especially in Kitab, Shahrisabz, Yakkabog, Guzor and Karshi districts. About ten points of the action strategy are devoted to the development of tourism, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev this year

The priority tasks defined in his speech at the meeting of the video selector with representatives of the Oliy Majlis chambers, political parties and the Environmental Movement of Uzbekistan on July 12 will further increase our responsibility. For example, it is possible to implement many projects on the development of a new terminal of the international airport, the protection of the life and health of tourists and excursionists when organizing visits to tourism facilities, and the development of ecotourism. In other districts of the region, a number of projects were presented, such as increasing tourist routes, making the best use of existing opportunities, further developing ecotourism, and organizing trips to the deserts of Mubarak district. The implementation of programs aimed at the development of tourism was analyzed, and proposals and recommendations were discussed regarding the unopened tourism directions and unused opportunities of Kashkadarya.

Creating a tourist map of each district in the region, adopting a program of measures for the development of ecotourism, providing preferential loans to young entrepreneurs who want to work in the direction of tourism development, simplifying the procedure for issuing licenses to tourist companies, agrotourism, ethnographic tourism Development, expansion of hotel and service service opportunities, improvement of tourist routes and regional reserves to world standards were defined. In the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, approved by the decree of the President on January 28 of this year, the task of developing the infrastructure of tourism and cultural heritage objects and adopting the state program for the effective use of more than 8 thousand cultural heritage objects is defined. This is a serious basis for the development of pilgrimage tourism in our country. Pilgrimage is one of the oldest

forms of travel and has a spiritual basis. The word "Ziyarat" is derived from Arabic and means "to go (come) to see". In Muslims, pilgrimage usually means visiting holy places, while in other religions and peoples, it corresponds to the concept of traveling around the world. It refers to a pilgrimage to religious or secular holy places away from one's permanent residence. Literally speaking, pilgrimage is when people go to holy places and perform certain actions there, and receive spiritual and spiritual nourishment. In addition, pilgrimage helps people to reach spiritual and physical maturity. While mass tourism is physical recreation, pilgrimage tourism is spiritual recreation. At the same time, it plays an important role in the formation and strengthening of the national idea and unity as an important segment of the development of sustainable tourism.

It is necessary to distinguish religious and secular types of pilgrimage. The first is based on divine and the second is based on universal human values. If religious pilgrimage means going to holy places, persons, places where saints are buried, secular pilgrimage is expressed in visiting and appreciating natural, historical and vital places. Worldly pilgrimage is a journey closely related to perfect human education. On the Day of Remembrance and Appreciation, it is possible to place a wreath at the foot of the "Mourning Mother" statue, visit the "Martyrs' Memorial" complex in Tashkent, the tomb of Amir Temur in Samarkand, visit the ancient and eternal cultural center of Bukhara or the Ichan Fortress in Khiva.

Pilgrimage tourism has great social and spiritual significance. Visiting holy places gives an opportunity to communicate with the spiritual experiences of a person in an industrial society. Pilgrimage tourism creates favorable conditions for reuniting families. It helps to grow socially, to strengthen human solidarity, fraternity, and to form a person as a person. Reduces social and racial segregation. In ancient times, when there were no modern means of transport and communication, it was customary to visit the tomb of Qusam ibn Abbas, who was buried in Shahizinda. This complex is still crowded with pilgrims. Also, the tombs of Imam Bukhari and Khoja Daniyol in Samarkand, Hazrat Khizr Mosque, Yetti Pir memorial ensemble in Bukhara, Hakim Termizi and Abu Isa Termizi mausoleums in Surkhandarya are among the holy places. Pilgrimage tourism is difficult to distinguish from other forms of tourism, of course. Those who come to visit the holy places do not limit themselves only to the tombs of the saints.

They want to see other interesting historical and cultural objects and architectural monuments of the cities. They get acquainted with the lifestyle, traditions, customs, values, and modern life of the local population. Uses city and intercity transport and means of communication. He eats national dishes and buys various souvenirs and national clothes. So, the economic and financial importance of pilgrimage tourism is also great. At the same time, among those who are interested in business, business trips, the country's history, economy, culture, and congress visitors, there are not a few people who visit religious objects - mosques, madrasas, saghanas and mausoleums. Most of the visitors to the city of Tashkent do not leave without visiting the Khastimom (Hazrati Imam) complex.

People who come for pure pilgrimage are mainly elderly, full of themselves, people who work with calculations. They don't like spending too much. Therefore, naturally, he does not go to various entertainment places. In addition to great spiritual, political, and social benefits, pilgrimage tourism also has various financial resources and expenses, the appropriate use of which not only fully covers the expenses, but also brings benefits. Moreover, not all services provided to visiting tourists are free. In recent years, a number of measures have been implemented in our country to develop pilgrimage tourism as a branch of general tourism, to strengthen its material and technical base, to improve its infrastructure, and to provide the sector with medium-specialized and highly qualified personnel. In particular, the mausoleums of our great ancestors, who made a great contribution to the development of Islam, were improved, mosques and madrasas, special hotels for religious scholars were built, and gardens were

established around them. Currently, 2 research institutes, 4 colleges, 6 technical schools and the "Silk Road" international university of tourism and cultural heritage are operating in the system of the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage in order to train highly qualified specialists in the field of domestic and pilgrimage tourism.

Qualified foreigners and foreign-educated specialists teach at the university. There is also a master's degree in pilgrimage tourism. This holy land, which has given great gifts, attracts foreign tourists, especially pilgrims. As the President noted, the information package of pilgrimage sites has not yet been fully formed, the mechanism of using innovative digital factors in the organization of pilgrimage has not been created, and the maps of pilgrimage sites are not at the required level. In this regard, it is urgent to create an electronic integration platform of pilgrimage tourism in our country. Taking into account this issue, such an electronic platform is being created at the International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan on the basis of a state grant. This project is to create a single integrated register of major sacred sites, unique objects, architectural monuments, cultural, spiritual and material resources in our country based on international experience, sacred sites, unique objects, architectural monuments, cultural, spiritual.

In particular, an international airport serving tourism has been launched in Samarkand. The airport has the potential to serve 800 passengers per hour, operate in the "open sky" mode, and increase the number of regular flights from 40 to 120 per week. Independent experts note that there is an opportunity to increase the flow of passengers through the airport from 480,000 to 2 million people per year. Based on foreign experience, work has been started on the establishment of night shopping complexes and service stations serving tourists and guests in potential cities and districts. Initially, conditions for tourists are being created in the cities of Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva. By achieving a 24-hour service for tourists, employment will be ensured. Similar domestic and pilgrimage tourism infrastructure is being created in almost all regions of our country.

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